

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation:

Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including
communication activities

Project name	CONFIDENTLY CHANGING COLONIAL HERITAGE
Project acronym	CONCILIARE
Project number	101132582
Call	HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01-04
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting authority	European Research Executive Agency
Start date	1 March 2024
End date	28 February 2027
Duration	36 months
Coordinator	University of Coimbra
Project coordinator (PCO)	Joaquim Pires Valentim
CORDIS link	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101132582
Project officer KOM ppt	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ZMg_57eLDPI3spd5bjblw4RIbAwZpWt3/view

Deliverable title	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities
Deliverable number	14
Deliverable version	1
Contractual date of delivery	31 st august 2024
Actual date of delivery	30 november
Nature of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work Package	WP5
Task(s)	Tasks 5.1, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5
Partner responsible	UM
Author	Giovanna Leone, Mihaela Gavrilă, Vincenzo Maselli, Rosa Cabecinhas, Isabel Macedo, Teresa Forte

Abstract	In D5.1, we present CONCILIARE's "Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities". The plan intends to ensure the long-term impact of the project outreach and results, by engaging, educating and empowering relevant target groups, through distinctive brand management, dissemination actions and publishing materials.
Keywords	Project Management; Dissemination; Communication; Exploitation

List of partners

UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA (Portugal) - **UC**

UNIVERSITE LIBRE DE BRUXELLES (Belgium) - **ULB**

UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT (Netherlands) - **UU**

UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO (Portugal) - **UM**

UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA (Italy) - **US**

ARCHIVES GENERALES DU ROYAUME ET ARCHIVES DE L'ET (Belgium) - **AGR**

HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO (Finland) - **HU**

INSTITUT DRUSTVENIH ZNANOSTI IVO PILAR (Croatia) - **IP**

AFROPEAN PROJECT (Belgium) - **AF**

CENTRO DE ESTUDOS SOCIAIS (Portugal) - **CES**

ICOM Belgique Wallonie-Bruxelles (Belgium) - **ICOM**

CONCILIARE (“Confidently changing colonial heritage”) is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research programme under grant agreement number 101132582. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Cite as: Leone, Gavrilă, Maselli, Cabecinhas, Macedo & Forte (2024): CONCILIARE. Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities. CONCILIARE project: “Confidently changing colonial heritage”.

This document is shared under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	8
2. Introduction and Objectives.....	8
3. Dissemination and Communication Strategy.....	12
3.1. Target Groups.....	12
3.2. Communication and dissemination infrastructure.....	21
3.3. Key dissemination activities and channels.....	24
3.4. Project visual identity and website.....	33
3.5. Dissemination policy, rules and procedures.....	52
3.6. Planning and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities	57
4. Exploitation Strategy.....	61
ANNEX 1: C&D Guideline for partners.....	71

Abbreviation Index

CCH | Colonial Cultural Heritage

CCI | Culture and Creative Industries

CDE | Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

DMP | Data Management Plan

EC | European Commission

EU | European Union

FAIR | Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability

GA | Grant Agreement

IPR | Intellectual Property Rights

KER | Key Exploitation Results

KPI | Key Performance Indicator

NGO | Non-Governmental Organizations

REA | European Research Executive Agency

TG | Target Group

WP | Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Deliverable D5.1 “Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities” intends to ensure the long-term impact of the project outreach and results, by engaging, educating and empowering relevant target groups, through distinctive brand management, dissemination actions and publishing materials.

This document is developed as an “**open**” **document** with ongoing updates according to context-related project needs. It includes a broad approach to the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy, contemplating main goals and a list of action points to achieve them; specification of target groups; detailed list of tools, channels and materials for achieving actions; visual identity and marketing of the project; a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) and a plan for exploitation/update of the results.

The communication, dissemination and exploitation activities plan will be devised from the start and updated in function of the know-how derived from the co-creation processes path, considering the increase in knowledge of target audiences and appropriate outreach as well as the enduring legacy of the activities.

In terms of dissemination and communication (as developed in Task 5.2 and 5.3), the CDE plan will: **(1)** propose communication activities, a dissemination strategy and define the objectives of the actions; **(2)** identify the targeted audiences for each objective or main results (dissemination as in Task 5.2); **(3)** list the communication and dissemination channels to be used for project promotion; **(4)** present a schedule of the communication and dissemination actions all along the project duration; **(5)** Describe the monitoring and implementation of impact assessment actions (through qualitative and quantitative measures).

2. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The CDE Plan is developed under the framework of Work Package (WP) 5, “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation” and Task 5.1 of the CONCILIARE project; nevertheless, it will interact with the remaining WPs to ensure a meaningful and long-term impact of the project outreach and results. Also, WP5 certifies that the work developed throughout the lifespan of the project has a full impact both in terms of the production of new knowledge and in developing operational recommendations and policies for future implementation by policymakers and stakeholders.

Firstly, to familiarize ourselves with the topic, it’s important to clarify the related terms – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation – in a way that makes it easy to distinguish them, as presented in Table 1¹². Such an approach assists readers in comprehending the content of the CDE Plan.

¹² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/dissemination-and-exploitation-research-results_en. And also “Horizon Europe Glossary: a simple guidance through HEU terminology”. Available at: <https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-04/HE%20Glossary%20Bridge2HE.pdf>

Table 1. Definition of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation according to the European Commission

<p>Communication</p>	<p>Communication is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about: (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange, and as a iii) means of internal communication between the teams and among the project partners. The process encompasses informing about the project and promoting its results and success.</p>
<p>Dissemination</p>	<p>Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including scientific and other publications and actions that increase awareness of the project and its results in any medium. The transfer of knowledge and results (free of charge) is aimed to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximizing the impact of EU-funded research.</p>
<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>Exploitation refers to the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities. Besides commercial, exploitation may be societal, political, or intended to increase public awareness and participation. Exploitation focuses on the actual use of the results, translating research concepts into concrete solutions that have a positive impact on the public's quality of life.</p>

The overall objective of WP5 is to conduct and supervise the interconnected activities of communication, dissemination, and exploitation of CONCILIARE results. The University of Minho will lead WP5, in close articulation with UC as a co-leader and cooperate with all partners that will be actively engaged from the start. The development of the activities will draw on processes of co-creation with stakeholders from culture and creative industries (CCIS) and we will pay special attention to tailor the materials to the main 7 target groups (Table 2), namely: (1) academic and research community; (2) community cohesion stakeholders; (3) educational stakeholders; (4) museums and national libraries stakeholders; (5) policy and decision makers; (6) citizens and wider society; (7) media (and journalists). This WP5 aims to ensure that the main findings and innovative materials and tools tested through the small-scale pilots integrate each target group's understanding of the changes in the EU's colonial heritage while enabling them to face these changes with confidence towards a common perception of European history. WP5 aims at capacitating and engaging stakeholders with innovative ways of fostering counter-narratives on colonial heritage and its changes that may also apply to other types of heritage and political and social spheres, integrating project results into educational and institutional proposals. The general objective is articulated in specific objectives:

- Ensure the creation and ongoing update of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan of activities;
- Ensure maximum visibility of the project through activities and communication tools adapted to different audiences;
- Implement and develop diverse activities to maximize the outreach of the results: creation of a website, fostering a strong social media presence, co-produce SNS accounts and a web archive of project visuals, press releases, organize workshops to reach and engage with civil society and the network of the consortium partners;
- Identify different potential routes for innovation and exploitation of the project results to maximize, extend and sustain the post-project impact on a large range of stakeholders.
- Develop and implement a set of initiatives to reach and involve policymakers.

In this frame, it is essential to identify the **objectives** of the CDE Plan (Figure 1) because they will guide the strategy throughout the project. Communication of project objectives, work and results will begin at the outset of the project and continue during the project lifespan. All consortium partners are also expected to actively engage in communication activities using their organisation's communication channels.

Figure 1. General Goals of the CDE Plan

To achieve a deeper understanding of the ongoing cultural change and its potential to build confidence (EO1), the CDE Plan outlines the following objectives:

- Raise awareness on the importance of turning current controversies regarding traces of colonialism into opportunities towards more confident, inclusive and respectful European societies;
- Inform about the cultural heritage linked to past colonial times and the related violence while engaging and empowering the target audiences to face with confidence and trust the changing nature of overseas colonial past;
- Develop imaginative, interactive and inclusive tools of communication (e.g., a podcast related to colonial heritage; short documentaries, thus also fostering training and new opportunities in CCIs);
- Create an attractive, engaging and user-friendly interface to aggregate all the communication resources deployed for the outreach and dissemination activities.

To validate the news methods employed, tested in small scale (EO2), the CDE Plan puts forth the following objectives:

- To share updates with the network on the pilot's ongoing experiences from all work packages, hence contributing to their fine-tuning and further developments;
- To create a "How we did it" guide with the methodology, process, and recommendations to facilitate future replications across the cultural, geographic, political and socio-economic diversity of Europe.

To achieve the above objectives, the CDE Plan stipulates:

- Communication and dissemination goals and list of action points to achieve them;
- Specification of target groups, their interests and influence in the project, as well as scope and form of the follow-up activities to increase CONCILIARE reach and impact;
- A detailed list of tools, channels and materials demanded to fulfil the mentioned actions;
- A visual identity of the project and a list of necessary marketing and promotional activities;
- A set of key performance indicators (KPI) for various aspects of the plan through the project lifespan;
- A follow-up plan to foster exploitation and update of the results.

Dissemination, exploitation, and communication are interconnected activities, all relating to the envisaged tasks and all important to ensure that the project delivers maximum impact and achieves its intended outcomes. WP5 will be dedicated to CDE measures based on clear goals and tailored content to specific audiences. UM will lead WP5, in articulation with UC as a co-leader, and all partners will be actively engaged from the start. In addition, all media materials, audiovisual and multimedia production will have UM supervision, even when developed by partne

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The CDE Plan must promote the project actions and its results by providing **targeted information to multiple audiences** (including the media and the public) in accordance with the objectives and rules stated in the GA and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.

The CDE plan will be available to all project partners as a valuable instrument that is expected to be updated throughout CONCILIARE's lifetime with the know-how derived from the co-creation processes path.

3.1. Target Groups

The **communication, dissemination and exploitation** activities were designed considering the following target groups who will be asked to participate, provide insight and input, and be actively involved in the communication actions.

Table 2
Target Group 1 - Academic and Research Community

Target and end-user group (direct benefit)	Potential Entities to be contacted	When/How	Responsible partner	Scope of engagement
-Research organizations within the humanities and social sciences interested in CONCILIARE results and innovations, able to use them in their own research: history, sociology, psychology, communication and society, educational science, social sciences, anthropology.	<p>Brussels Studies Institute (Belgium) https://bsi.brussels/fr/recherches/</p> <p>Focus area Migration and societal change (Netherlands) https://www.uu.nl/en/research/migration-and-societal-change</p> <p>High Schools in Center Region of Portugal, under the frame of the program Ciência Viva, run by CES (Portugal)</p> <p>TUMO (Coimbra, Portugal)</p> <p>Scientific Council for the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. https://www.fct.pt/en/sobre/a-fct/organizacao/conselhos-cientificos/conselho-cientifico-das-artes-humanidades-e-ciencias-sociais/</p> <p>Historians without borders in Finland, Research Community for Humanities and Social Sciences Education (Finland)</p> <p>Secondary Schools in Braga, Guimarães, Porto (Portugal)</p> <p>Team “Résolution Métis,” Belgian State Archives (Belgium) https://www.arch.be/index.php?l=fr&m=nos-projets&r=projets-de-recherche&pr=projet-resolution-metis#3</p> <p>The Equality, Diversity and Inclusion programme (Netherlands) https://www.uu.nl/en/organisation/equality-diversity-inclusion/edi-programme</p> <p>The Steering committee regarding slavery past and colonialism (Netherlands) https://www.uu.nl/en/organisation/about-us/tradition-and-history/slavery-past/steering-committee</p> <p>Université Catholique de Louvain – project “Re-member” (Belgium) https://uclouvain.be/fr/instituts-recherche/ispole/cecri/arc-re-member.html</p> <p>Université libre de Bruxelles – project “Hericol” (Belgium) https://hericol.ulb.be</p> <p>University of Algarve (Portugal)</p> <p>University of Coimbra (Portugal)</p> <p>University of Minho (Portugal)</p> <p>University of Porto (Portugal)</p> <p>University of Lisbon (Portugal)</p>	Ongoing: as contacts will be made according to research and project development	<p>University of Minho and University of Coimbra</p> <p>Utrecht University</p> <p>Université Libre de Bruxelles</p> <p>ICOM Belgique Wallonie-Bruxelles</p> <p>University of Helsinki</p> <p>Center for Social Studies (CES)</p>	Engage for communication, collaborative research and workshops

Table 3
Target Group 2 - Community Cohesion Stakeholders

Target and end-user group (direct benefit)	Potential Entities to be contacted	When/How	Responsible partner	Scope of engagement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionals working with ethnic minorities and migrants - Community managers of social network platforms - Social workers - Local municipality - Civic society association, artists and/or performers addressing the issue of colonial heritage - Afro-descendant organizations (or diaspora communities) - Youth-led movements/organizations that are advocating awareness about the legacy of colonialism in society (not yet concrete which organizations) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Afro Dutch (Netherlands) https://afrodutch.org Africa Cultural Promotion Center (ACPC) (Netherlands) http://theacpc.nl African and Caribbean Heritage Network (ACHN) – from Utrecht University (Netherlands) Association Bamko-cran (Belgium) Association Village du Monde (Belgium) Associação Cultural e Juvenil Batoto Yetu (Portugal) Associação Cultural Moinho da Juventude (Portugal) Associação Unidos de Cabo Verde (Portugal) Bakushinta (Belgium) Belgium for Peace (Belgium) Bibliothèque Lumumba (Belgium) Café Congo (Belgium) Casa de Angola (Portugal) Casa de Angola em Coimbra (Portugal) Casa do Brasil (Portugal) Change (Belgium) CHOICE for Youth and Sexuality (Netherlands) https://choiceforyouth.org Collectif Mémoire Coloniale et Lutte contre les Discriminations (Belgium) https://www.memoirecoloniale.be Collective Faire-part (Belgium) Djass (Portugal) Expeditie de Stad Vzw (Belgium) Geheugen Collectief (Belgium) Hand in Hand tegen racisme (Belgium) ICOM (Belgium) https://icom.museum International Federation for Public History (IFPH) (Belgium) https://ifph.hypotheses.org ISPP (Belgium) https://www.ispp.org Maison de la Mémoire de Mons (Belgium) Mémoires du Congo (Belgium) Migrant Rights Collective (Belgium) Network of Concerned Historians (Belgium) http://www.concernedhistorians.org Plateforme associative « Décolonisation de l'esprit et de l'espace public » (Belgium) Quinoa (Belgium) https://www.quinoa.be Tala Tala (Belgium) UMAC (Belgium) https://umac.icom.museum Wetsy Gallery (Belgium) Youth at Heart (Netherlands) 	<p>Communication and contacts will be done according to communication plan and following agenda of exhibition, programs, events or seminars</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> University of Minho Utrecht University + Afropean Project Université Libre de Bruxelles Université Libre de Bruxelles ICOM Belgique Wallonie-Bruxelles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate on exhibitions and educational programs and other events or public seminars Raise awareness and promote dialogue on cultural heritage Facilitate discussions on history

Table 4
Target Group 3 - Educational Stakeholders

Target and end-user group (direct benefit)	Potential Entities to be contacted	When/How	Responsible partner	Scope of engagement
- Teachers' associations, educational authorities, at European, national, and local levels	European Association of History Educators (Euroclio) European Trade Union Committee for Education (ETUCE) Local Schools Board of Management, from Consortium Countries	Communication and contact will be made by all partners regarding the development of research and projects These targets are also necessary every time there are relevant results to share, in order to promote discussion	University of Minho and University of Coimbra	Raise awareness and promote dialogue on cultural heritage Facilitate discussions on history

Table 5
Target Group 4 - Museums and National Libraries Stakeholders (and other cultural organization)

Target and end-user group (direct benefit)	Potential Entities to be contacted	When/How	Responsible partner	Scope of engagement
<p>- Museums and heritage institutions across Europe related to colonial history, whether or not they have colonial collections.</p> <p>- Local Municipalities.</p> <p>- Associations for the development of art and urban redesign.</p>	<p>AfricaMuseum (Belgium) https://www.africamuseum.be</p> <p>Ateneu de Coimbra. ateneudecoimbr a1940@gmail.com</p> <p>Batoto Yetu Portugal – Cultural and Youth Association (Portugal) <i>(No specific website found)</i></p> <p>Casa da Cultura (Coimbra)</p> <p>Caixa Negra Círculo de Iniciação Teatral da Academia de Coimbra - Associação (CITAC)</p> <p>Centro Internacional das Artes José de Guimarães (Portugal) https://www.ciajg.pt</p> <p>Convento de S.Francisco https://www.coimbraconvento.pt/pt/</p> <p>Hemeroteca (Lisboa). https://hemerotecadigital.cm-lisboa.pt/</p> <p>Marionet - Associação Cultural (Portugal) marionet@mari oneteatro.com</p> <p>Mons Memorial Museum (Belgium) https://www.monsmemorialmuseum.mons.be</p> <p>Museu de Lagos (Portugal) https://www.cm-lagos.pt/en/descobrir-lagos/museus-e-centros-de-interpretacao/museu-municipal-dr-jose-formosinho</p> <p>Museu Virtual da Lusofonia (Portugal) https://www.museuvirtualdalusofonia.com</p> <p>Museum aan de Stroom (Museum MAS) (Belgium) https://www.mas.be/en</p> <p>National Museum of Ethnology (Lisbon) (Portugal) https://www.patrimoniocultural.gov.pt/en/museus-e-monumentos/rede-portuguesa/m/national-museum-of-ethnology</p> <p>National Museum of World Cultures (Netherlands) https://www.wereldculturen.nl/en</p> <p>Portal Buala (Portugal) https://www.buala.org/en</p> <p>Royal Institute of Natural Sciences (Belgium) https://www.naturalsciences.be</p> <p>Teatro da Cerca de S.Bernardo (Coimbra, Portugal) https://weblog.aescoladanoite.pt/</p> <p>Teatrão - Companhia de Teatro de Coimbra (Portugal) https://www.oteatro.com</p> <p>TAGV - Teatro Académico Gil Vicente, Coimbra (Portugal)</p>	<p>Contacts with these institutions must be an ongoing matter. These contacts must be done to ensure exhibitions, educational programs and other events.</p> <p>Everytime an event is scheduled specific local audiences must be targeted within 10-15 days in advance and also invitations to press/media.</p>	<p>University of Minho and University of Coimbra</p>	<p>Collaborate on exhibitions and educational programs and other events or public seminars;</p>

Table 6
Target Group 5 - Policy and Decision Makers

Target and end-user group (direct benefit)	Potential Entities to be contacted	When/How	Responsible partner	Scope of engagement
<p>Polymakers (local/national/EU): This is a wide group encompassing local, regional, national authorities, representatives and associations, Ministries, parliaments and Public Administrations at national, European and international levels.</p>	<p>Alto Comissariado para as Migrações (ACM) (Portugal) https://www.acm.gov.pt</p> <p>Brussels working group "Decolonisation of Public Spaces in the Brussels-Capital Region" (Belgium)</p> <p>CCDR NORTE – CULTURA (Portugal)</p> <p>CCDR CENTRO- Cultura (Portugal)</p> <p>City of Antwerp (Belgium) https://www.antwerpen.be/en</p> <p>City of Brussels (Belgium) https://www.brussels.be</p> <p>City Council of Coimbra (Portugal). https://www.cm-coimbra.pt/</p> <p>City of Mons (Belgium) https://www.mons.be</p> <p>Commission royale des Monuments et des Sites (Royal Commission on Monuments and Sites) (Belgium)</p> <p>Councillors for culture and education in the Municipalities of Braga, Guimarães, Porto, Faro and Lisboa (Portugal)</p> <p>Direction du Patrimoine culturel (Directorate of Cultural Heritage) (Belgium)</p> <p>Directorate-General for the Arts (DGARTES) (Portugal) https://www.dgartes.gov.pt</p> <p>FARO – Vlaams steunpunt voor cultureel erfgoed (Flemish Institution for Cultural Heritage) (Belgium) https://www.faronet.be</p> <p>Finnish National Agency for Education (Finland) https://www.oph.fi/en</p> <p>Ministers of Culture, Ministers of Scientific Research at the community, national, and EU levels from the countries of the Consortium</p> <p>Municipalities of Lisbon and Lagos (Portugal)</p> <p>Lisbon: https://www.lisboa.pt</p> <p>Lagos: https://www.cm-lagos.pt</p> <p>Stad Antwerpen – Borgerhout Bewaart & Littekens van Borgerhout (Belgium)</p>	<p>Communication with these audiences is key since they are regulators and policy makers.</p> <p>Open meeting and forums for discussion must be scheduled. There are no specific dates, since every partner must ensure that this channel is open.</p> <p>Publication and public dissemination of research results must always include these policy makers in form of direct contacts, e-mail messaging, meetings and public invitations for relevant events.</p>	<p>University of Minho and University of Coimbra</p>	<p>Influence policies around education and cultural heritage;</p> <p>Advocate for policies supporting cultural heritage education and preservation;</p>

Table 7
Target Group 6 - Citizens, wider Society and countries outside of the consortium

Target and end-user group (direct benefit)	Potential Entities to be contacted	When/How	Responsible partner	Scope of engagement
<p>Citizens of different cultural origins, paying special attention to descendants of colonized groups, and a wider audience – with a special focus on enhancing communication between older and younger groups of citizens.</p>	<p>Local Entities and Associations</p> <p>Media Outlets from countries of the Consortium</p> <p>Social Media Bloggers / Influencers</p> <p>Universities:</p> <p>Agostinho Neto University (Angola)</p> <p>Amílcar Cabral University (Guinea-Bissau)</p> <p>Catholic University of Angola (UCAN) (Angola)</p> <p>Eduardo Mondlane University (Mozambique)</p> <p>Federal University of Bahia (UFBA) (Brazil)</p> <p>Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG) (Brazil)</p> <p>Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ) (Brazil)</p> <p>Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS) (Brazil)</p> <p>Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP) (Brazil)</p> <p>Higher Institute of Education (ISE) (Cape Verde)</p> <p>Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU) (India)</p> <p>National University of Timor-Leste (UNTL) (Timor-Leste)</p> <p>Peking University (China)</p> <p>Pedagogical University of Mozambique (Mozambique)</p> <p>State University of Campinas (UNICAMP) (Brazil)</p> <p>Tata Institute of Social Sciences (TISS) (India)</p> <p>Tsinghua University (China)</p> <p>University of Brasília (UnB) (Brazil)</p> <p>University of Cape Verde (Uni-CV) (Cape Verde)</p> <p>University of Delhi (India)</p> <p>University of Kinshasa (Democratic Republic of the Congo)</p> <p>University of Kisangani (Democratic Republic of the Congo)</p> <p>University of Lubumbashi (Democratic Republic of the Congo)</p> <p>University of São Paulo (USP) (Brazil)</p>	<p>Communication must be done according to plan and events scheduled with a focus on preparing information with relevancy for citizens and wider society</p>	<p>University of Minho with all partners of the Consortium</p>	<p>Raise awareness and promote dialogue on cultural heritage</p> <p>Collaborate on cross-border initiatives and share best practices</p> <p>Partner on global initiatives and share knowledge regarding heritage</p> <p>Engage in discussions around colonial histories and their contemporary relevance</p>

Table 8
Target Group 7 - Media/Press and Journalists

Target and end-user group (direct benefit)	Potential Entities to be contacted	When/How	Responsible partner	Scope of engagement
<p>Media and Press (TV's, Magazines, Newspapers...)</p> <p>The detailed list provides a comprehensive overview of media contacts in each country involved in the CONCILIARE project, as well as key European media outlets. By reaching out to these contacts, you can effectively disseminate information about the project and engage a wide audience.</p>	<p>Belgium Belgium Revue Politique Martin Georges redaction@revuepolitique.be RTBF La matinale Patrimoine rtbfpro@rtbf.be Un jour dans l'histoire (RTBF) rtbfpro@rtbf.be Arabel FM Tarik Laabi tariklaabi@hotmail.com Le Vif Anne-Sophie Bailly as.bailly@levif.be Le Soir Colette Braekman colettebraeckman@yahoo.fr Le point Afrique Marlène Panara marlene.panara@gmail.com abo@lepoint.fr</p> <p>Croatia Večernji Dijana Jurasić dijana.jurasic@gmail.com vecernji@vecernji.hr News 24sata Ana Dasović ana.dasovic@24sata.hr redakcija@24sata.hr NOVA TV Lora Dizdar lora.dizdar@novatv.hr novatv@novatv.hr Index web portal desk@index.hr HRT hrt@hrt.hr</p> <p>Finland Finland Ulkopoliitikka Taina Tervonen tainatervonen@orange.fr toimitus@ulkopoliitikka.fi Europe Politico Camille Gijs cgjjs@politico.eu editorial@politico.eu Helsingin Sanomat hs.online@hs.fi Yle News ylenews@yle.fi Aamulehti al.toimitus@aamulehti.fi Helsinki Times Alexis Kouros (Editor) alexis@helsinkitimes.fi info@helsinkimes.fi University of Helsinki The University's communications specialists comms-citycentre@helsinki.fi</p> <p>Italy La Repubblica larepubblica@repubblica.it Il Sole 24 Ore Francesca Barbiere francesca.barbieri@ilssole24ore.com Arte Magazine redazione@artemagazine.it Netherlands NRC nrc@nrc.nl De Volkskrant redactie@volkskrant.nl Trouw opin@trouw.nl</p> <p>Portugal RUM - Rádio Universitária do Minho António Ferreira RUC- Rádio Universidade de Coimbra admin@ruc.pt Agência Lusa agencialusa@lusa.pt RDP África Paulo Borges Fernanda Almeida Público Joana Gorjão Henriques joanagh@gmail.com Ana Cristina Pereira Ana.Cristina.Pereira@publico.pt Observador observador@observador.pt</p>	<p>According to events, workshops activities and results presentations, media must be contacted/invited. Maintaining constant contacts with journalists is relevant and key for the success of this activity.</p>	<p>All partners of the Consortium</p>	<p>Raise awareness and promote dialogue on cultural heritage</p> <p>Engage in discussions around colonial histories and their contemporary relevance</p>

	<p>Jornal de Notícias secdir@jn.pt jn.online@jn.pt Jornal É@gora Manuel Matola (Mozambican journalist) +351937 416 343 Other Contacts (Portugal) A Mensagem, Afrolink, Bantumen, Buala, Centro de Média Independente, Comboio Suburbano - Podcast, Crónico, Dezanove, Divergente, Duas Linhas, esQrever, Fumaça, Gerador, Guilhotina.info, Hedflow, Interruptor, Jornal Mapa, JUP - Jornal Universitário do Porto, Libertária, O Lado Negro da Força, Página Um, Portal Arnaquista, PTrevolutionTV, QiNews, Rádio Zero, Revista Manifesto, Revista Rua, Rua FM, Shifter, SinalAberto.</p> <p>European-Level Media Contacts EuroNews (Lyon) +(33) 4 28 67 00 00 Politico Europe editorial@politico.eu EUobserver Alejandro Tauber at@euobserver.com The Brussels Times info@brusselstimes.com</p> <p>Other Countries RM Rádio de Moçambique Ouri Pota pacamutondo@gmail.com TVM Televisão de Moçambique Vicente Nhacumba viceamo@gmail.com</p>			
--	--	--	--	--

3.2. Communication and dissemination infrastructure

Communication of project objectives, work and results will begin at the outset of the project and continue throughout its lifecycle. All consortium partners are expected to actively engage in communication activities, using their organization’s communication channels. In the table below, the activities are distributed by two dimensions, related to visual identity and communication infrastructure and the communication of CONCILIARE results to different audiences.

Table 9: Communication and dissemination infrastructure

1. Design CONCILIARE visual identity and communication infra-structure				
Target group	Instrument	Activity and output	Responsible Partner	Time
All TGs	CDE	<p>A comprehensive communication strategy is being developed for the project, encompassing key messages, the identification of specific target audiences across various national and international contexts, and a social media strategy. This strategy defines a cohesive visual identity (logo, color palette, fonts, templates for reports and presentations) and establishes a clear brand identity across digital platforms, including the website and social media layouts. Inputs from consortium partners are integrated to ensure alignment with their perspectives and goals, providing consistent guidelines for all partners.</p> <p>The general strategy aims to standardize communication efforts across the consortium, ensuring that all partners have clear and unified guidelines for impactful project representation.</p> <p>In parallel, the Exploitation Strategy will focus on promoting awareness, participation, engagement and further impact on society.</p>	UM with input from all partners	October / November 2024
All TGs	Website/ platform	<p>The website is an interactive platform to communicate the project’s mission, aims, latest news, reports and publications as well as embed all the media digital tools (directly or through links). The website link is as follows: https://conciliare.eu.</p>	UC, SU, UM	October 2024. The deadline had to be extended, due to available data and programming

2. Communicate CONCILIARE channels to different audiences				
Target group	Instrument	Activity and output	Responsible Partner	Time
All TGs	Website/ platform	The scientific and research content to be communicated will be provided by each partner and uploaded to the website https://conciliare.eu . It will be kept updated in articulation with social media and with tailored tools to all groups (text, audio, audio-visual). Translation and adaptation to impaired audiences will be provided.	UC, SU, UM	From November 2024
TG1 and TG5	EC channels	Updated project's results and news in Horizon magazine and CORDIS.	UC	Entire duration of the project.
All TGs	Social Media	Different social media channels (Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn) will be used to communicate projects' news and relevant information linked to the Website and as directed in the content strategy for social media.	UM	November 2024.
TG1- TG7	Newsletter	Newsletter to promote the project, partners, research and work and also to extend the communication to stakeholders and partners. The newsletter will be published every two months.	UM	November 2024.
All TGs	Media materials	The media contents to be co- created with CreateLab (UM) and MEDIALAB (SU) based on input from all the partners will be embedded in user friendly and widely accessible platforms, such as the channels of CECS (UM), and then disseminated via social media accounts and the project website. The media material will include printed material for events/conferences and activities, as well as videos of the project (presentations, testimonies, events, research activities). Recording of podcasts.	UM and SU	Starting from January 2025 and for the entire duration of the project.
TG7	Press releases	Press releases should be in English for larger European Institutions and in native language of the country (if required) of publication. These will inform about the projects results and activities to traditional media outlets to enhance the visibility of the project, also reaching groups with lower digital literacy.	UM leading with all partners of the project, considering the activities and country of the activity. UM will supervise.	Starting from the kick off meeting (march 2024) and for the entire duration of the project.
TG5 and TG7- UC	Policy briefings and leaflets	Brief and engaging infographics to communicate core messages and results to be shared across website and social media.	All partners, coordinated by UM	From the 18th month of the project.

All TGs	Project events	Co-created engagement initiatives, including art happening and installations; workshops, popularizations, exhibitions and meetings.	All partners, coordinated by UM	During the whole project.
All TGs	Final conference	A final conference will be organized bringing together all stakeholders and will be web-streamed to maximize the outreach.	UM with input from all partners	The final conference will be scheduled in one of the last three months of the project.

3.3. Key dissemination activities and channels

In line with the design phase, the following table provides an overview of the communication activities and key channels for dissemination that are planned for specific targeted groups guided by four main goals: 1) to strengthen research and innovative knowledge; 2) to promote co-creation processes with key actors from culture and creative industries (CCIs) and educational stakeholders; 3) to empower key relevant actors in dealing with changes in colonial heritage with confidence, and 4) to develop international and cross-sectorial partnerships to transfer knowledge during and after the project terminus. The detailed communications strategy for the project was devised by SU, UM, and UC (with input from WP leads), including core messages, identification of specific target audiences per national context, and a distinctive visual identity (logo, color, fonts, template for reports, presentations).

In addition, an **internal mailing list** includes all the partners in the project's interactions, and **online meetings** will take place to discuss progress and outstanding issues. Meetings with other relevant actors, networks and EU-funded projects will be pursued for joint dissemination and communication actions. Each partner will leverage their dissemination networks and channels to promote the project.

Key dissemination activities and channels

1. Strengthen Research & Innovative Knowledge

Publications

Publications in high-ranking/ international scientific journals - *Target Group 1*

Examples of target journals:

- Annals of Tourism Research
- Brussels Studies
- British Journal of Social Psychology
- Comunicação e Sociedade
- Current Sociology
- Ethnic & Racial Studies
- European Journal of Social Psychology
- European Journal of Teacher Education
- Group Processes and Intergroup Relations
- ICOM Advances in Museum Research Series
- International Journal of Intercultural Relations
- Journal of Museum Education
- Journal of Postcolonial Studies
- Journal of Social and Political Psychology
- Journal of Social Issues
- Journal of Travel Research
- Key Concepts of Museology
- Lusophone Journal of Cultural Studies
- Memory Studies
- Museum & Society
- Museum Anthropology
- Museum International
- Political Psychology
- Postcolonial Studies
- Papers on Social Representations
- Race, Ethnicity & Education
- The International Review of Social Psychology
- Tourism Geographies

Papers produced/published in 2024

Kesteloot, C. (2024). L'histoire au bout de la rue. Le passé dans l'espace public bruxellois. *Passés Futurs*, 15, June 2024. <https://www.politika.io/fr/article/lhistoire-au-bout-rue-passe-lespace-public-bruxellois>

Kesteloot, C., & Rilla, J. (2024). Davantage qu'une simple plaque... Odonymie et espace public. *Passés Futurs*, 15, June 2024. Coordination of the dossier "Odonymie et espace public".
https://www.politika.io/sites/default/files/documents/numero-revue/fichier/PF15%20juin%202024%20-%20Politika.io__2.pdf.

Yasmina Zian, Book review "Julie Bawin, Art public et controverses XIXe-XXIe siècle, 2024.", *Contemporanea*, to be published.

Yasmina Zian, Book review "Africa's Struggle for its Art: History of a Postcolonial Defeat by Benedicte Savoy", *The Journal of Development Studies*, to be published.

Presentations at international conferences

Target Groups: TG1-2- 3-5-7

Examples of targeted conferences:

- AfroEuropeans Network Conference
- Annual Meeting of the International Society of Political Psychology
- Annual conferences of several ICOM International Committees (such as COMCOL, the International Committee for Collections; CECA, the International Committee for Education and Cultural Action; ICMEMO, the International Committee for Memorial Museums in Remembrance of the Victims of Public Crimes; UMAC, the International Committee for University Museums and Collections)
- Atlas Annual Conference
- BeMuseum (the annual Belgian conference on innovation in museums)
- Conference of the AfroEuropeans Network
- Conference on the Future of Europe
- Conference organised by the House of European History
- Conferences of the IRAHSSE's network (International Research Association for History and Social Sciences Education)
- Critical Tourism
- Euroclio Annual Conference
- European Sociology Association Research Network Meetings
- General Meeting of the European Association of Social Psychology (EASP, e.g., 2026)
- International Conference of Europeanists
- International Conference of the International Federation for Public History
- International Conference on Memory Studies 2025
- International Conference on Social Representations 2025
- TAPAS Conference (TAPAS/Thinking About the PAST is an interdisciplinary forum for reflection on various relationships with the past)
- Triennial General Conference of ICOM (next one in Prague this month of August and then in Dubai in 2025) which is the world museum ideas exchange platform

Attended and Future Conferences with participation planned

Date: 11-13 July 2024

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Name: Conférence Internationale de Psychologie Sociale: Symposium "Héritages du colonialisme et relations intergroupes actuelles"

Link to event website: [CIPS-LF 2024](#)

Date: 3rd-4th October 2024

Location: University of Coimbra (FPCE), Portugal

Name: International Social Psychology Workshop. Colonial legacies in print: Textbooks from the 1950s to the present day

Participants: Joaquim Pires Valentim, Teresa Forte, Emiliano Abad Garcia, Felix Meuer, Ana Cabrita (University of Coimbra; Coordinator of CONCILIARE; co-leader of WP1) Inari Sakki (University of Helsinki; co-leader of WP1) Giovanna Leone (University of Rome 'La Sapienza'; WP1 Participant) Aline Bosuma, François Makanga, Mars Florin (AfroPean, Brussels; WP1 Participant) Karel van Nieuwenhuysse (Catholic University of Leuven; WP1 external expert).

Date: 16-17 Octobre 2024

Location: Lyon, France

Name: Une approche sociétale des crises

Link to event website: <https://psysocietale.sciencesconf.org/>

Participants: Joaquim Pires Valentim & Teresa Forte (University of Coimbra). "Are Portuguese dictatorship shadows fading? Psychosocial legacies in values and colonial representations". Teresa Forte, Alina Coriolano, Ana Cabrita, Felix Meuer & Joaquim Pires Valentim (University of Coimbra). "How foreign is the past?": Political communication of Portuguese colonial ideology thinking". Felix Meuer, Teresa Forte, Joaquim Pires Valentim, Alina Coriolano & Ana Cabrita (University of Coimbra). Representations of colonial history in Portugal: A study on Portuguese textbooks"

Date: 24 October 2024

Location: Mons

Name: Transmettre la mémoire – Journée d'étude

Participant: Chantal Kesteloot Title: "La médiation Culturelle au service de la mémoire collective ».

Link to event website: <https://mundaneum.org/activite/transmettre-la-memoire/>

Date: 14 November 2024

Location: Brussels

Name: La toponymie bruxelloise d'hier et de demain

Participant: Chantal Kesteloot Title: La toponymie bruxelloise d'hier et de demain

Link to event website: <https://bsi.brussels/fr/research/toponymie-bruxelloise/>

Date: 20-22 November 2024

Location: Madrid

Name: Decolonizing Museums and Resignifying Monuments

Link to event website: International Congress - Decolonizing Museums and Resignifying Monuments

Participants: Joaquim Pires Valentim (University of Coimbra - presenting CONCILIARE project) Giovanna Leone (La Sapienza University of Rome): "Reading the colonial material intermediations in the silence of societal awareness: The case study of Italy". Felix Meur

(University of Coimbra): “Representations of colonial history in Portugal- A Study on Portuguese Textbooks”. Rosa Cabecinhas (University of Minho): “Unsettling the afterlives of the Empire: Memory activism and the decolonization of public space in Portugal”. Emiliano Abad García: Discussant and member of the organizing committee.

Date: 29-30 April 2025

Location: Braga, CECS - Universidade do Minho

Name: Migration and Communication in a Planetary Age

Link to event website: [Conference on Migration and Communication](#)

Date: 28-30 May 2025

Location: Porto, Portugal

Name: XII Simpósio Nacional de Investigação em Psicologia

Date: 19-20 June 2025

Location: Utrecht, Netherlands

Name: Migration and Societal Change Conference - Showcases the Latest Scientific Research and Policy Innovations on Migration, Contributing to Public Discourse and Encouraging Fresh Perspectives

Link to event website: [Migration and Societal Change Conference](#)

Date: 04-06 June 2025

Location: Neuchâtel, Switzerland

Name: Spoliations, Restitutions et Circulation des Objets: Pour une Géopolitique du Patrimoine

Link to event website: [Calendar Event](#)

Date: 1-4 July 2025

Location: Paris

Name: IMISCOE Annual Conference - Decentering Migration Studies

Link to event website: [IMISCOE 22nd Annual Conference](#)

Date: 3-6 July 2025

Location: Prague

Name: ISPP Annual Meeting - Social Identity, Political Conflict, and the Future of Democracy

Link to event website: [ISPP Annual Meeting](#)

Date: 8-11 July 2025

Location: Faculté des Lettres et Sciences Humaines, Université de Bretagne Occidentale, Brest, France (Supported by the Réseau Mondial Serge Moscovici - REMOSCO)

Name: XVIIth International Conference on Social Representations - The Future in Representations: Grasping Our World

Link to event website: [International Conference on Social Representations](#)

Date: 14-18 July 2025

Location: Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague

Name: Ninth Memory Studies Association Conference “Beyond Crises”

Link to event website: [Memory Studies Association Conference](#)

Briefs, Articles and technical reports

Target Groups - TG2 to 5 and 7

- Research briefing in which the main results and interpretations will be presented in a non-technical manner and explanations of how they can be used to work with specific groups such as youth, females, ethnic minorities, and minorities (TG2).
- Technical report on recommendations for teaching the history of colonialism and facing changes in CCH and other types of heritage with confidence.
- Technical report on the changes in CCH and controversies in public spaces and facing ongoing changes with confidence.
- European Policy Brief focused on policy implications of WP1-WP4 findings for social cohesion, positive intergroup relations in European societies.
- Technical report on the current exhibitions in the studied museums (see Capacity of participants and consortium as a whole) and the transformations since 2000.
- Technical report on contested ownership case studies in the studied museums (see Capacity of participants and consortium as a whole).
- Technical report on visitors' spontaneous exploration of expositive spaces dedicated to colonial collections and narratives.
- Technical report on visitors' perceptions and emotional reactions to colonial collections and narratives.
- National research briefing in PT and NL.
- Popular articles: articles accessible to a general audience published on platforms like the conversation France, InMind (French, Dutch, English, German language versions), appearance by French-speaking members on the podcast Milgram de Savoires.

Articles for national and international newspapers; interviews for TV, Radio and the Web

Target Groups: All TGs

The scientific results described in the previous point will also be disseminated to a wider audience through the development of more simplified and accessible materials such as articles, interviews and short videos to be published in magazines, national and local television, websites and social network sites. An important vehicle for disseminating the intermediate and final results of the project are the university radio stations, starting with the Italian Raduni network and reaching the university broadcasters in the other consortium countries.

Open access and the availability of Results

Target Groups – TG1

Open access to data, stored in an open access database, including metadata.

2. Promote co-creation processes with key actors from culture and creative industries and education stakeholders

Co-creation of media education tools with CCI's

Target Groups: All TGs

- Digital stories on narratives about traces of contested colonial heritage and facing changes with confidence conveyed through.
- Short documentaries with the analyzed visuals, text and researchers' insight and strategies on how to contextualize the topic and develop pedagogical activities.
- Podcast interviews (leaders/researchers) about the most relevant findings across countries and national findings and their social, policy and practical implications.
- Short animated videos detailing the main activities and achievements of the project and raising awareness on sensitive topics.
- Series of radio drama through RadUni circuit. In recent years, especially with the success of podcasts, there has been a resurgence of this ancient narrative genre of radio drama. There is a return to radio theatre, which allows one to enter the dynamics of events and identify oneself, above all when dealing with social problems or historical events.
- An integration of traditional forms of dissemination and comprehension with multimedia narratives could generate more empathy with the different targets and a better understanding of colonialism and its consequences, cultivating confidence in a multicultural future of Europe.

Documentary

Target Groups: All TGs

Documentary on CONCILIARE research within the museums, produced by the Master in Media Studies and Journalism of Sapienza University (MEdiaLab/Radio Sapienza) and disseminated through social networks and, in particular, through Radio Sapienza's YouTube channel.

Co-creation of engagement initiatives

Target Groups: All TGs

Art happenings, street exhibitions, street comics, street photographic projects and street installation projects.

3. Empower key relevant actors in dealing with changes in colonial heritage with confidence

Guidelines, recommendations, policy briefs

Target Groups: TG2 and TG5

Tutorial guidelines, technical reports on recommendations for approaching the topic of colonialism and communicating colonial heritage changes with confidence across Europe; policy recommendations, policy briefs.

Courses and training

Target Groups: TG1 and 5

Lessons in the framework of the CIVIS open course on collective memories and colonial exhibitions, in collaboration with WP1 excerpt from Universidad Autónoma of Madrid, ULB, and SU.

Courses Planned:

Name: Training & Pilot Session for Focus Groups within WP4

Date: End of October 2024

Location: Utrecht University

Target Audience: Researchers from each country involved in conducting/facilitating the focus groups

Name: Framing decolonial debates and practices in Portugal (provisory title)

Date: April-May 2025 (still to be fixed)

Location: Coimbra University

Target Audience: researchers in social sciences, post graduate students, activists and community organizations dealing with decolonial issues

Events

Target Groups: All TGs

- EU event organized at the House of European history; national events organized with the competent authorities for each museum (municipalities, Ministries, etc.).
- Popularization Events: at least one participation of the researchers of the project in events for science popularization like the International Museum Day (May 18th), EU researchers' night, ESOF conference, Pint of science, science fairs, or other generic events.
- Museum meetings in studied museums, starting from Museum of Civilizations in Rome (IT), AfricaMuseum in Tervuren (BE), the Afrika Museum in Bergen Dal (NL).

- Final infoday/event (All TG).
- All events will have an online component to maximize their reach.
- Chantal Kesteloot will participate in the 11 November commemoration organized by Bakushinta Association, in Brussels.

Participation in Events

Date: 21 October 2024

Location: Universidade do Minho, Braga

Name: Seminar on Communication & Diversity (SDC)

Target Audience: Researchers from the CONCILIARE project and beyond

Link to event website: [Seminar on Communication & Diversity](#)

Date: 11 November

Location: Place François Riga, Schaerbek Riga

Name: 11th November Celebration

Partipation: Chantal Kastellot

Target Audience: wider society

Date: 28 April 2025

Location: Universidade do Minho, Braga

Name: Visões Descoloniais: Património Colonial, Processos de Descolonização e Cultura Visual / Decolonial Visions: Colonial Heritage, Decolonising Processes and Visual Culture

Target Audience: Researchers from the CONCILIARE project and beyond

Date: 26 November 2024

Location: Ivo Pilar Institut, Zagreb

Name: Ivo Institute Celebration Day – Conciliare Presentation

Target Audience: Researchers from the CONCILIARE project and beyond

Date: March-April 2025

Location: University of Coimbra

Name: "Mapping controversial colonial heritage in Portuguese cities"

Target audience: graduation and graduate students; community of scholars and researchers of the University of Coimbra; cultural and civic associations in Coimbra

Newsletter

Target Groups: All TGs

Every two months newsletter providing information on CONCILIARE progress, events, activities, and impact. A link to the subscription to the newsletter and a downloadable version will be available on the project website. Newsletter areas and directions to consortium partners can be found in the Annex.

Press Releases

Target Groups: TG7

- Press releases to traditional media outlets (local, regional and national press, radio) will be prepared informing about activities and main results, enhancing its visibility across different audiences, including those with lower digital literacy.
- The first contributions are already available on the radiosapienza.net website and other information platforms.
- The language must be adapted to country of media. For European Media Press releases will be sent in English.

3.3.1. Open science

For effective communication and dissemination of results, CONCILIARE partners are advised to work within an open science ecosystem, enabling access, particularly, to scientific publications and research data, and ensuring that no conflict with Intellectual Property Rights security rules or legitimate interests is in place. This will allow the collection, processing and distribution of data from and to multiple stakeholders.

Open science practices need to be assured by Horizon Europe beneficiaries. As stated in the Grant Agreement (GA), a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In those situations, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests. All these cases will be verified and supervised by the project leader.

CONCILIARE beneficiaries shall comply to the following rules in order to ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results:

- At the latest at the time of publication, a digital copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, needs to be deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publication. All of these measures will comply with copyright laws and the corresponding book publishers' policies;
- Immediate open access must be provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND);
- Information must be given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication;
- Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements;
- Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles;

-Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

The open science principles also apply to the Data Management Plan (DMP), to be developed according to the Research Ethics.

Regarding authorship and ownership, data collection is conducted by CONCILIARE team members, and it's owned by the beneficiary that generates it. Beneficiaries will grant access to other members of the consortium upon written request. It is set that CONCILIARE country teams first work on their respective national data which they collected themselves. Beyond this, all CONCILIARE team members are encouraged to publish together or in cooperation. Joint publications are seen as an excellent way to disseminate the project results and to enhance the comparative element of the project.

3.4. Project visual identity and website

The CONCILIARE project visual identity and website are a project deliverable (D5.2) implemented at month 3 (and continuously updated). The logo was essential in establishing the **visual identity of CONCILIARE**, and the website represents the **main communication and dissemination channel** between partners and all target groups, and it will serve as a repository for all public deliverables and project materials.

Partners undertook an extensive co-creation process to develop the project logo – to ensure that it represented the essence of the project. After a series of proposals and redesign actions the final visual identity concept encapsulates the essence of intangible cultural heritage, cultural history, and confident approach in embracing a past made of tradition and diversity through a harmonious blend of color, shape, and typography. The chosen colors – beige, green, orange, and clay – represent the earth's natural palette, symbolizing the rich cultural histories rooted in diverse landscapes (Figure 2). Beige stands for tradition and history, grounding the visual identity in cultural heritage. Green reflects growth, renewal, and the enduring vibrancy of living traditions. Orange evokes warmth, creativity, and the spirit of human connection, while clay symbolizes the foundational aspects of human culture, echoing the craftsmanship of ancient practices.

Figure 2: Color palette

The logo (Figure 3) is composed as a juxtaposition of shapes inscribed in a squared matrix. These Geometric yet rounded shapes are employed to convey rigor, order but also relaxation, confidence and unity signifying the project's aim to bring together diverse cultures in a cohesive manner. These shapes are softened to suggest trust, fluidity and adaptability, mirroring the ever-evolving nature of cultural heritage and suggesting how to approach and enhance it.

Figure 3: Logo

The typography used for the logo is CAVIAR DREAMS in bold and regular style (Figure 4). This typographic character is elegant yet approachable, with soft curves and balanced proportions, embodying the project's emphasis on confidence and accessibility. This typographic choice ensures legibility at any size while maintaining a universal aesthetic, reinforcing the project's global reach and commitment to preserving and celebrating cultural diversity.

Figure 4: Font used in the Logo

For the website, we chose a more minimalistic type font - "inter" - to pair with more dynamic and engaging visual elements and enhance readability and legibility on different types of screens and media.

The CONCILIARE website (<https://conciliare.eu/homepage/>) has the following objectives:

- **Present the project**, including information about context, objectives, work plan and the consortium;
- **Promote project results**, communicating news, deliverables, events, activities and other non-confidential information;

- **Publish and interact with other communication channels and tools**, including social media, events, and newsletters.

From a composition perspective, the website intends to be a visually appealing and thoughtfully designed platform that combines a modern minimalistic aesthetic with a palette evoking cultural heritage associated with the earthy tones of the logo.

In order to include more appealing and colorful images without stimulus overloading or impairing the readability and immersion with the text information, we kept the earthy tones of the logo in a minimalistic setting.

The layout of the website is vertical, guiding users naturally as they scroll down the page. The design is based on geometric shapes with the colors of the logo (distinct from section to section).

The figures below serve as previews for the in-depth content found in the various subsections of the website. Each box features an image or visual element that represents the content it links to, making navigation intuitive and visually engaging. The images are carefully selected to reflect the cultural, historical, and project-related themes of the website, enriching the user's experience and providing context for the information presented.

The homepage is designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the site's content. It is structured in a way that allows users to quickly find the information they are looking for, with each subsection clearly delineated and easily accessible. To convey a more dynamic and engaging experience, the boxes with images are asymmetrical.

The homepage serves as a gateway to five main subsections: "the project", "what we do", "who we are", "news & events", and "resources". Each of these subsections is designed with a focus on clarity and user engagement and gives access to other pages.

The "project" page provides an overview of the socio-cultural and historical context in which the project is situated and offer users a deeper understanding of the project's background (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Screenshots of "the project" section

The “what we do” section includes the description of the workpackages. To convey a more dynamic and engaging experience, the carousel displays different images related to each WP and the symbols in dark clay inspired by CONCILIARE logo move across the image.

Figure 6: Screenshots of “what we do” section

WP1- Textbooks

WP2- Public Spaces

WP3- Museums

WP4- Culture & Traditions

The "who we are" page offers a comprehensive overview of the institutional partners and individuals involved in the project. It includes profiles of key team members, descriptions of partner organizations driving the project, and links that give direct access to the involved universities official websites.

Figure 7: Screenshots of the “who we are” section

The “news & activities” section on the homepage provide an overview of the past and upcoming events organized within the project or closely linked to it. Each event is framed in a box that provides the main information, a short description and a link that that opens to the poster or the web page of the event.

The website is a well-structured and visually appealing platform that effectively communicates the project's essence while offering users an engaging and informative browsing experience and has a mobile version that contains the same information and pages as the desktop version but with a different layout.

Other materials – including the Word and PPT templates – were also developed. These materials will be available throughout the span of the project.

3.4.1. Social Media

Engagement through appropriate social media platforms is an effective way for targeted outreach and for fostering two-way communication. Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn were selected as the social media channels to be used to disseminate information, publications, and events from the project. Hence, the project was kick-started by creating the following communication channels, as anticipated:

- Facebook:** <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61569347811616>
- Instagram:** https://www.instagram.com/conciliare.eu/?igsh=MW55am0xbHl1cmEycA%3D%3D&utm_source=qr
- LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/conciliareeuropeanproject/>

Figure 8: CONCILIARE’s Front Page on Facebook

Figures 9 and 10: CONCILIARE’s Front Page on Instagram and LindedIn

The UM team, as leading partner in WP5, has a person fully dedicated to the WG5:

Julia Vilhena julia.vilhena@ics.uminho.pt

In addition to using CONCILIARE social media accounts, partner organizations will collectively contribute towards enhancing the visibility of these profiles through their respective organizational accounts for enhancing the overall effectiveness of communication.

Each partner will have an **active coordinator** to make it easier to share contact with the communication team, as follows:

Figure 11: Partner Contacts for Communication and Content

Archives Generales Du Royaume Et Archives De L'Et

Isabelle Ponteville Events and Communication Manager

E-mail: Isabelle.Ponteville@arch.be

For Communication content:

Alana Castro

E-mail: alana.castrodeazevedo@arch.be

Chantal Kesteloot

E-mail: chantal.kesteloot@arch.be

Afropean Project

Lina Bosuma

E-mail: mamalinao@gmail.com

ICOM Belgique Wallonie-Bruxelles

Alexandre Chevalier

achevalier@naturalsciences.be

Institut Društvenih Znanosti Ivo Pilar

Marina Maglić

E-mail: Marina.Maglic@pilar.hr; +385 98 967 9347

Social media

Marina Maglić

E-mail: Marina.Maglic@pilar.hr; +385 98 967 9347

Helsingin Yliopisto

Aino Santavuori

E-mail: aino.santavuori@helsinki.fi

For social media:

E-mail: digiviestinta@helsinki.fi

Universita Degli Studi Di Roma La Sapienza

Giovanna Leone

E-mail: giovanna.leone@uniroma1.it

Université Libre de Bruxelles

Yasmina Zian

E-mail: yasmina.zian@ulb.be 0032477920914

For social media

Yasmina Zian

E-mail: yasmina.zian@ulb.be 0032477920914

University of Coimbra

Emiliano Abad Garcia

E-mail: abadgarcia@uc.pt

Center for Social Studies (CES)

Claudino Ferreira

E-mail: claudino.ccf@gmail.com

For social media content:

Pedro Dias da Silva

E-mail: gestorinfo@ces.uc.pt

University of Minho

Rosa Cabecinhas

E-mail: cabecinhas@ics.uminho.pt +351918108018

For social media

Júlia Vilhena

E-mail: julia.vilhena@ics.uminho.pt

Pedro Menezes

E-mail: pedromenezes89@gmail.com

Utrecht University

Eveline Meeuwissen (Communication & Marketing FSBS)

Email: cenm.fsw@uu.nl /

For social media

Nazgol Salamat

E-mail: n.salamat@uu.nl

The project will also link with the EC social media, as a means to integrate the community of Horizon Europe projects: @HorizonEU, @EU_Commission, @REA_research.

Below, we present the detailed Content Strategy for social media.

3.4.1.1. Content Strategy for Social Media

Objectives

Based on the plan’s objectives, we have highlighted the specific goals for social media.

Raise Awareness: Provide visibility of the CONCILIARE project, focusing on understanding of colonial heritage and its implications for contemporary society.

Engage the Community: Foster community involvement by promoting participation in dialogues, workshops, and cultural events related to the cultural heritage linked to past colonial times and violence related to colonialism.

Educate and Inform: Provide educational resources and information about colonial heritage to diverse audiences, including educators, policymakers, and the general public.

Facilitate Collaboration: Strengthen partnerships with cultural and educational institutions to promote co-creation processes and knowledge sharing.

Promote Events: Ensure that workshops, conferences, and cultural heritage days are well-publicized and attract a broad audience.

Brand Identity on Social Media: Tone of Voice for the CONCILIARE Project

To achieve these objectives and to establish brand coherence through social media, it is recommended that CONCILIARE follow the tone of voice of the brand. The tone of voice of the project is focused on five key characteristics.

Table 10: CONCILIARE’s Tone of Voice

<p>Educational and Enlightening</p> <p>CONCILIARE is committed to elicit a critical debate and broader understanding of the narration and narratives regarding history and colonial cultural heritage. This commitment is transversal to the four envisaged dimensions: textbooks, public spaces, museums and cultural consumption. The tone is straightforward and clear, making complex information accessible without oversimplifying, helping the audience reflect on the relevance of the past and respective narratives for both the present and future.</p>
<p>Respectful and Reflective</p> <p>When addressing historical themes, the tone, albeit thought-provoking, will be respectful and empathetic, highlighting the importance of treating diverse cultural and historical experiences with dignity. The focus is on encouraging reflection, debate about the possibilities of addressing colonial cultural heritage and fostering respect for a variety of cultural narratives</p>
<p>Inclusive and Dialogue-Oriented</p> <p>CONCILIARE aims to be a space where everyone feels invited to participate in meaningful conversations. The tone is inviting and inclusive, encouraging the audience to share their insights</p>

and take part in collaborative dialogues, reinforcing the notion that different perspectives enhance shared understanding.

Collaborative and Academic on LinkedIn

On LinkedIn, where the audience is more professional and academic, the tone remains formal and collaborative, highlighting the value of partnerships and academic discussions. This tone reinforces CONCILIARE's credibility and its focus on working with institutions to enrich understanding of the project's aims.

Inspiring and Visually Engaging on Instagram

On Instagram, the tone is inspiring and visually descriptive, encouraging the audience to engage with the posts in an accessible and compelling way. The language is inviting and reflects the value of cultural stories and memories.

Content Plan by Social Media

The Content Plan guides the communication team through the project's publishing content, including the objectives **for each social media, the frequency of posts, optimal times for publication, types of posts, and the adaptation of the visual identity for social media.** To ensure coordinated communication, a publication calendar is suggested at the end of the Content Plan.

It is important to note that each partner will have an **active coordinator** to facilitate the sharing of content with **the communication team.** Note that coordination is essential for key moments with partners, such as launches, events, and milestones.

Posts at closely timed intervals will also be implemented to reinforce the project's digital presence across all partners' social media. To ensure consistency, **it is recommended that all partners use the project's hashtags, as indicated below.** During major events or launches/releases, there will be reposting in Stories and live updates.

At the end of each month or after important events, it is advisable to analyse engagement and posts reach. This monitoring will enable the communication strategy to be adjusted and optimised, while also facilitating shared feedback between the project and its partners for continuous strategic alignment and strengthening of the collaborative network.

Facebook

Main Objective: Inform and engage the public about the CONCILIARE project.

The proposal is to publish 2-3 weekly posts on the feed that will be focused on informative content, partnerships, and events. Posts are preferably made on Tuesdays, Wednesdays, and/or Fridays, between **10:00-12:00** or during the afternoon from **15:00-18:00**, according to the local time zone. These times generally maximise reach and engagement, particularly on weekdays when professionals and institutions are more active. It is worth noting that posts involving partners have to take into account the local time zones.

Types of Posts:

Overview of the Conciliare Project:

Objective: To inform the audiences about the project and to keep them updated on key dates and milestones.

Content: Posts explaining CONCILIARE's goals, the project's aims on social media, and the importance of its studies. These posts will include image carousels and/or short videos to make the information more dynamic.

Frequency: 1-2 times per month and on milestone dates or important project dates.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareProject #CulturalMemory #ColonialHeritage #ConnectedNarratives #CulturalExchange

Meet the Team and Partners:

Objective: To highlight the people behind the project and the partners involved.

Content: Posts dedicated to team members and institutional partners, possibly including short interviews and video testimonials in mini-documentary formats.

Frequency: Weekly, with a focus on new partners or team members.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareTeam #CulturalPartnerships #HistoricalConnections #ConnectingStories #CulturalExchange

Case Studies and Research:

Objective: To share results from studies, ongoing research, and impact testimonials.

Content: Detailed posts on specific cases, new studies, and important advancements, featuring quotes from those impacted. Infographics may be used to simplify complex data. A monthly podcast format will also be introduced, with episodes dedicated to specific case studies and testimonials, lasting 15 to 20 minutes each.

Frequency: Weekly, as new research updates become available.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareStudies #CulturalIdentity #ColonialHeritage #ReconstructingMemories

Events:

Objective: To promote and cover events such as workshops, seminars, and conferences.

Content: Pre-event announcements with details as location, date, and speakers, and post-event summaries with photos and acknowledgements to participants.

Frequency: According to the events calendar, with one post before and one after the event.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareEvents #CulturalPresence #HistoryInAction

Stories:

Objective: To connect the public to the project's behind-the-scenes, live events, and reinforce feed posts.

Content: Behind-the-scenes clips, event coverage, quick updates on new feed content.

Frequency: Daily during events and 2-3 times per week for general updates.

Instagram

Main Objective: Visually engage the public and spark interest through **educational and interactive** content.

The proposal is to publish 2-3 weekly posts on the feed, focusing on visual and informative content, partnerships, and events. Similar to Facebook, posts are preferably made on Tuesdays, Wednesdays, and/or Fridays, between **10:00-12:00** or in the afternoon from **15:00-18:00**, according to the local time zone. Posts involving partners have to consider local time differences.

Types of Posts:

Overview of the Conciliare Project:

Objective: To introduce audiences to the project and to keep them informed about important dates and milestones, with a strong visual emphasis.

Content: Posts explaining CONCILIARE's goals, the project's social media goals, and the significance of its research. These posts will feature image carousels and/or short videos to enhance engagement.

Frequency: 1-2 times per month and on milestone or important project dates.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareProject #CulturalMemory #ColonialHeritage #ConnectedNarratives #CulturalExchange

Meet the Team and Partners:

Objective: To humanise the project and strengthen connections by showcasing the people involved.

Content: Posts dedicated to team members and institutional partners, possibly including Reels with mini-interviews and video testimonials in a mini-documentary format.

Frequency: Weekly, focusing on new members and key partners.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareTeam #CulturalPartnerships #HistoricalConnections #ConnectingStories #CulturalExchange

Case Studies and Research:

Objective: To visually showcase the project's advancements and ongoing research.

Content: Posts on specific cases, new studies, and key findings, featuring quotes from those impacted. Infographics, Reels, and carousels will present new studies, discoveries, and testimonials. Monthly podcast episodes will also be introduced, each dedicated to a specific case study, lasting 15 to 20 minutes.

Frequency: Weekly or as new research updates become available.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareStudies #CulturalIdentity #ColonialHeritage #ReconstructingMemories

Events:

Objective: To promote and cover events, including workshops, seminars, and conferences.

Content: Visual pre-event and post-event announcements, including behind-the-scenes photos and live coverage via Stories.

Frequency: According to the events calendar, with Story coverage during events and one feed post before and after each event.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareEvents #CulturalPresence #HistoryInAction

Stories:

Objective: To create an immediate connection with the audience and highlight real-time events.

Content: Behind-the-scenes clips, event coverage, quick updates on new feed content, interactive polls, and quizzes.

Frequency: Daily during events and twice per week for general updates.

LinkedIn

Main Objective: To highlight the academic and institutional impact of CONCILIARE, focusing on education and collaboration.

The proposal is to post 2-3 times monthly, featuring in-depth content, interviews, articles, studies, and invitations to participate in events. Posts are recommended for Tuesdays, Wednesdays, and/or

Thursdays, between **08:00-10:00** and/or in the afternoon between **13:00-14:00**, according to the local time zone. These times correspond to peak professional activity on the platform. Posts involving partners have to consider local time zones.

Types of Posts:

Interviews:

Objective: To share insights from specialists and the Conciliare team.

Content: Posts that highlight interviews with team members, partners, or specialists, discussing topics such as the challenges and importance of preserving memory through cultural dialogue.

Frequency: Monthly, especially when introducing new collaborations or experts.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareInterview #CulturalDialogue #ConciliareTeam #MemoryInAction

Opinion Articles:

Objective: To provide in-depth, academic analyses on project-related topics.

Content: Articles or long-form posts discussing cultural issues, offering insights that enhance discussions about heritage and society.

Frequency: Once per month.

Suggested Hashtags: #AcademicDialogue #ReflectiveMemory #EvolvingNarratives #ConciliareOpinion

Case Studies and Research:

Objective: To publish study results and updates on significant ongoing research.

Content: Comprehensive case studies and posts on the impacts of Conciliare, participant testimonials, and project advancements.

Frequency: 1-2 times per month, as new developments arise.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareStudies #CulturalIdentity #ColonialHeritage #ReconstructingMemories

Academic Events and Workshops:

Objective: To increase event participation and highlight institutional collaborations.

Content: Announcements for workshops, lectures, and networking events for professionals in the field, including registration links and speaker details.

Frequency: According to the events calendar, with posts before the event and a summary afterwards.

Suggested Hashtags: #ConciliareEvents #CulturalPresence #HistoryInAction

Brand Identity | Social Media Layout

To establish a visual standard for the target audience, the project's visual identity was adapted for social media posts.

Regarding background, the same colours from visual identity were adopted to maintain consistency. Additionally, gradients and shapes from the logo are used. The design approach also includes giving the posts a background reminiscent of a poster, featuring subtle textured grooves for added depth.

The logo is centred when the post is in a carousel format. For posts that are not in a carousel, the logo is left-aligned. Left alignment allows space for other partner logos. All posts include a mention of @conciliare at the top right side.

The font type was also adapted. For social media, the **Inter** typeface was chosen, as it is variable and works well on display. The maximum size to be used is 100 px for titles, and the minimum is 20 px (handle).

Below are the post templates, considering each content type.

Figure 12: Overview of the Conciliare Project section (with variations)

Figure 13: Meet the Team and Partners / Interviews section

Figure 14: Case Studies and Research / Opinion Articles section

Figure 15: Events (Pre) section

Figure 16: Events (Post) section

Figure 17: Stories / Reels covers

With the use of the logo's colors and shapes, the posts create a **dynamic feed**.

Figure 18: Dynamic Feed

Calendar Typology for Content Publication

This calendar typology for content publication ensures a consistent and varied presence across digital platforms.

Table 11: Typology of CONCILIARE’s Monthly Publications

Date	Platform	Content Type	Description
12/11/2024	Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn	Project Overview	Introduction to Conciliare, its mission and WG.
19/11/2024	Facebook, Instagram	Event Summary	Event summary with photos and participant highlights.
26/11/2024	Facebook, Instagram	Project Overview	Publication on a major milestone or achievement in the project.
03/12/2024	Facebook, Instagram	Meet the Team and Partners	Short interview introducing the role of a team member.
10/12/2024	Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn	Case Study and Research Update	Advancements in ongoing research.

3.4.2. Project newsletter: a collaborative writing strategy

The online newsletter aims to **inform, update, and engage subscribers** with relevant content and upcoming activities of the project. The CONCILIARE newsletter will be published every two months, on the project website and social media, as well as distributed via email to the consortium members and target audiences who have subscribed.

As for social media, the newsletters will be managed by communication team. It is important to remind that each partner will have an **active coordinator** to facilitate the sharing of content. In terms of the format, the newsletter will be short and flexible in structure, comprising key messages in 1-2 pages and including links for more detailed information, whenever suitable. A template for the newsletter was developed in Mailchimp platform, as shown in Figure 19.

The format is designed to cover all essential aspects of the project. It is divided into specific sections that each partner can populate with relevant information, as planned for social media. The following sections are included in the template:

-Case Study Selection: This section will highlight the case studies that have been selected for the month. Each partner is encouraged to provide details on the case studies they are working on, emphasizing the unique aspects of their research and its relevance to colonial cultural heritage.

-Conferences: Partners are invited to share details of any conferences where the project has been discussed or where related themes have been explored. This not only helps in showcasing the project's impact but also keeps the community informed about ongoing dialogues in the field.

-Achievements: This section will celebrate the milestones and achievements of the partners. Whether it's the successful completion of a research phase, a notable publication, or a significant recognition, partners are encouraged to share their successes to inspire and motivate the collective.

-Recent Publications: Keeping the subscribers updated with the latest research outputs, this section will list recent publications by the partners that are relevant to the project. It will serve as a resource for those interested in further reading and understanding the depth of research being conducted.

-Upcoming Events: Information about upcoming events organized by the research group or related to the project will be featured here. This includes workshops, seminars, and public lectures, offering opportunities for subscribers to engage with the project in real time.

-Project Advancement Actions: Looking ahead, this section will outline the actions planned for the next phases of the project. It provides a roadmap for the project's progression and helps maintain transparency and engagement with the subscribers.

To ensure that the newsletter is ready for distribution at the start of every two months, the **active coordinator** of the partners are required to submit their contributions by the middle of the previous month of the publication of the newsletter. A template will be provided to guide partners in their submissions, ensuring that the information is presented consistently and concisely.

This collaborative approach not only enriches the newsletter’s content but also fosters a sense of shared ownership among the partners. By contributing to the newsletter, each partner helps to shape the narrative of the project and ensures that it accurately reflects the collective efforts and insights of the entire team.

Discover CONCILIARE: Our Journey Begins

[READ MORE](#)

WELCOME

Welcome to this month’s CONCILIARE update! We’re excited to share our latest findings on colonial heritage and its contemporary impact. Join us at our upcoming workshop for insightful discussions!

EVENTS

Join us for the CONCILIARE Heritage Workshop on [date] at [venue]. Engage with leading experts in exploring the impact of colonial heritage on today’s society. The event will feature interactive discussions and networking opportunities. Reserve your spot now and be part of this transformative experience!

[READ MORE](#)

Figure 19: CONCILIARE’s Newsletter Template on Mailchimp

3.5. Dissemination policy, rules and procedures

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure,

equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must **acknowledge EU support** and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

“The CONCILIARE project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon - RIA Grant agreement n. 101132582”.

Figure 20: Funding acknowledgement emblem

In order to achieve effective communication and dissemination of the project activities and results, as well as community engagement, **all consortium partners should contribute to WP5 (Dissemination, communication and exploitation)**, collecting, creating and curating content, as well as using their activities and networks to promote the project’s outreach. In order to demonstrate how these contributions can be achieved, the table below develops some possible approaches in relation to activities or events.

It should be emphasized that the instructions to the partners are included in a simple C&D Guideline Document provided to partners and included in Annex 1.

Table 12: How partners should contribute to WP5

Event/Activity	How partners can contribute to WP5
<p>Participation on an external event</p>	<p>Distribute some of the brochures and flyers at the event and register the number distributed.</p>
	<p>Take pictures. It can be of the surroundings, the event itself (presentations, the room, etc.) or yourself in the event.</p>
	<p>Fill out this form (the form will be created and transmitted by e-mail); you can also email CONCILIARE (an email account is yet to be created) informing that you went to the event. Filling the form is preferable as we receive a notification and the information does not get lost.</p>
	<p>Fill this form (the form will be created and transmitted by e-mail); when planning/with the plan of the event.</p>
	<p>When inviting participants to the event via email, attach a digital brochure/flyer and register how many invites you send.</p>
	<p>Grab some of the brochures and flyers to distribute at the event and register the number of brochures/flyers distributed.</p>

Organising an event	Take photos, make short videos (of the surroundings, small parts of the event, short interviews, talk to the camera explaining what the event is all about, interview some of the guests/speakers, etc.
	Fill out this form (the form will be created and transmitted by e-mail); you can also email CONCILIARE informing that you went to the event. Filling the form is preferable as we receive a notification and the information does not get lost.
Participating on CONCILIARE related activity	If possible and if it makes sense to share, take photos and/or make short videos (of the surroundings, small parts of the meeting, short interviews, talk to the camera explaining what the event is all about, interview some of the guests/speakers, etc.
	Fill out this form (the form will be created and transmitted by e-mail); you can also email CONCILIARE informing that you went to the event. Filling the forms preferable as we receive a notification and the information does not get lost.
Publishing research paper/validated deliverable	If you just want to share what has been delivered, send an email to CONCILIARE to alert the partners that you've submitted your paper/deliverable (if it's public), for us to make it available on the website https://conciliare.eu .
	If you wish to share on social media some of the main results of your paper/deliverable, fill this form with some key information about the main results of your research paper, so it can be disseminated through CONCILIARE's virtual platforms and infographics can also be made if suitable.

Forms (Google Forms) will be developed to keep track of and analyze communication efforts made by partners, like events, publications and other activities. These aim to provide insight into communication status and KPI achievements.

Table 13: Communication activities register templates

Communication Efforts						
List of communication efforts made by partners.						
Partner(s) (Organization and Name)	Activity name and type (publication, news, etc.)	Date and place	Potential Outreach (Target groups and estimate number of participants)	Objectives (WP, KERs and impact)	Status of Dissemination (Planned/Completed)	Link / content
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						
13						
14						
15						
16						

Events			
Future events where the project should participate in or where you intend to participate in representing the project			
Partner(s) (Organization and Name)	Event name and type (meeting, conference, workshop)	Date and place	Link / content
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			

In regard to capturing images, video or other recordings, it is mandatory to **safeguard consent procedures** to ensure voluntary participation. All communication, dissemination and

exploitation strategies of the project adhere rigorously to ethical principles. These principles should also be applied to events, making sure that when participants register, they also give their consent to be photographed and filmed

3.6. Planning and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities

Qualitative KPI's will be assessed in a scale from 0 (insufficient) to 4 (excellent) covering the following dimensions: project progress (e.g. 'the overall project performs well'; 'communication between the consortium/team members runs smoothly'; 'team members reach goals without additional supervision'); scientific progress and deliverables (e.g. "deliverables and milestones are easily reached on time"; 'research hurdles are quickly and efficiently resolved'; 'the research benefits from the most recent research insights'); outreach: impact, dissemination and exploitation (e.g. 'The CDE is properly followed'; 'information regarding exploitation and dissemination of the results has been properly prepared for reporting to the European Commission"). To assess more objectively the success of the implementation, quantitative KPIS are presented below:

Communication plan

Table 14: Planning and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities

Dissemination & Communication activities	Target Audience							KPI's	
	TG1	TG2	TG3	TG4	TG5	TG6	TG7		
Dissemination									
Scientific papers in peer-reviewed international scientific journals	x	x	x	x				No. Publications	15
Date: Publish papers quarterly (if possible) Communication tactical procedures:									
<p>Social Media Previews - Share highlights of papers on LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook.</p> <p>Plain Language Summaries - Post accessible summaries on the project website and relevant platforms.</p> <p>Press Releases - Issue press releases, if relevant, for major findings to reach traditional and digital media.</p> <p>Newsletters to Academic Networks- Bi-monthly updates targeting research networks and mailing lists.</p> <p>Conference Presentations - Present findings at key conferences to engage the academic community.</p> <p>Use Partner Networks - Amplify publications via partner institutions' platforms.</p> <p>Visual Summaries- Create infographics for social media and the website to increase accessibility.</p> <p>Open Science Repositories- Upload papers and data to repositories and institutional databases.</p> <p>Video Summaries - Short videos on findings for social media and the project's pages.</p>									
Special issues in peer-reviewed international scientific journals	x		x					No. Publications	2
Date: At least once a year (June 2025) Communication tactical procedures:									
<p>Pre-Launch Teasers - Post sneak peeks on social media a week before release to build anticipation.</p>									

Email Announcement - Send a dedicated email to subscribers with highlights and a download link.

Social Media Campaign - Share key insights and visuals over multiple days on LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook.

Feature on Website - Highlight the special issue on the project website with easy access to download.

Cross-Promote with Partners - Ask partner networks to share the issue, providing ready-made posts and visuals.

Engaging Visual Content - Create infographics and visual summaries for social media and newsletters.

Press Release - Distribute to media outlets, focusing on the societal impact of findings.

Follow-Up Engagement - Respond to comments on social media to encourage discussion.

Reader Feedback Survey - Include a survey link in the issue to gather reader feedback for improvements.

Track Metrics - Monitor downloads, engagement, and other metrics to inform future issues.

Books	x							No. Publications	2
-------	---	--	--	--	--	--	--	------------------	---

Date: At least once a year (December 2025)
Communication tactical procedures:

Pre-Release Teasers - Share cover images and excerpts on social media a month before launch to build anticipation.

Launch Event - Host an online or in-person event featuring discussions or a Q&A with the authors to introduce the book.

Email Announcement - Send a detailed email to subscribers highlighting the book's themes, with a download or purchase link.

Social Media Campaign with Interviews - Post key quotes, visuals, and short interviews with the authors or experts discussing the book's content over several weeks.

Website Feature - Add a dedicated page on the project website with book details, a preview, and easy access to purchase or download.

Partner Promotion - Ask partner organizations to promote the book on their networks, newsletters, and social media.

Press Release - Issue a press release to relevant media outlets, focusing on the book's significance and unique insights.

Public deliverables	x	x	x	x	x			No. Deliverables	19
---------------------	---	---	---	---	---	--	--	------------------	----

Date: at least every 3 months
Communication tactical procedures:

Dedicated Website Section - Create a clearly organized section on the project website where all public deliverables are labeled, accessible, and downloadable.

Email Announcements - Send targeted emails to stakeholders and subscribers, featuring summaries and direct links to each new deliverable.

Social Media Highlights - Post key insights, graphics, and summaries from each deliverable on LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook to engage audiences and drive traffic.

Press Release for Major Deliverables - Issue a press release for significant deliverables that have high public or policy relevance, targeting relevant media outlets.

Video Summaries - Create short, engaging videos summarizing key points from each deliverable for social media platforms and the project website.

Partner Amplification - Encourage partners to share deliverables through their own networks, newsletters, and social media to maximize reach.

Quarterly Newsletter Updates - Include new deliverables in the project's quarterly newsletter with brief descriptions and links back to the website.

Organization of events/workshops	x	x	x	x	x			No. Events organized	10
----------------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	--	--	----------------------	----

Date: at least every 2/3 months
 Communication tactical procedures:

Pre-Event Teasers - Share teaser posts, countdowns, and highlights from previous events on social media to generate interest a few weeks before each event.

Event Registration Page - Create a dedicated registration page on the website with event details, speaker bios, agenda, and a simple signup form for easy participant registration.

Email Invitations and Reminders - Send targeted email invitations to stakeholders, partners, and subscribers with RSVP links. Follow up with reminders a week and a day before the event.

Social Media Campaign - Post key event details, including speaker introductions, workshop themes, and expected outcomes, on LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook leading up to the event.

Press Release for High-Profile Events - Issue a press release to announce major events or workshops that feature prominent speakers or address significant topics.

Live Social Media Updates - Share real-time updates, quotes, and photos from the event on social media platforms to engage both attendees and remote followers.

Post-Event Recap - Publish a summary of the event on the website and social media, including highlights, key takeaways, and photos. Send a follow-up email with a link to resources or recordings.

Participant Feedback Collection - Distribute a post-event survey to attendees to gather feedback on the event experience and improve future workshops.

Participation in scientific conferences/workshops	x	x	x	x	x			No. Events participated	12
---	---	---	---	---	---	--	--	-------------------------	----

Date: at least every 3 months
 Communication tactical procedures:

Abstract Submission and Pre-Event Promotion - Submit presentation abstracts early and, once accepted, announce participation on social media and the website with details about the conference and presentation topics.

Pre-Conference Teasers - Share short posts introducing the research to be presented, along with visuals or key questions that the presentation will address, to build anticipation among followers.

Conference Registration and Networking Preparation - Register key team members and schedule meetings with relevant researchers, collaborators, and industry professionals in advance to maximize networking opportunities.

Live Social Media Engagement - Post live updates, quotes, and images during presentations, panel discussions, or poster sessions on LinkedIn, Instagram, and Instagram to engage both attendees and remote followers.

<p>Highlight Key Findings and Takeaways - Share summaries of presentations and major takeaways immediately after the conference on the website and social media, emphasizing the relevance of the findings.</p> <p>Post-Event Blog or Newsletter Recap - Publish a blog post or include a section in the newsletter with a detailed recap of the event, highlighting insights, lessons learned, and networking outcomes.</p> <p>Follow-Up with Contacts and Leads - Send follow-up emails to new contacts made during the conference, sharing relevant research materials or links to project resources to strengthen connections and foster future collaboration.</p>									
Training and courses		x	x	x	x			No. Training organized	4
<p>Date: at least every 3/4 months Communication tactical procedures:</p> <p>Pre-Course Promotion - Announce the course on social media and the website, highlighting objectives, target audience, and instructor profiles.</p> <p>Registration Page - Set up a dedicated registration page with course details, learning outcomes, and a simple signup form.</p> <p>Email Invitations and Reminders - Send targeted invitations to stakeholders, with reminder emails a week and a day before the course.</p> <p>Social Media Updates - Share live updates and participant feedback during the course on LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram.</p> <p>Post-Course Recap and Feedback - Publish a course summary with key takeaways on the website.</p> <p>Certificates and Networking - Issue certificates of completion and invite participants to join a community for continued engagement.</p>									
Series of podcasts/ videos		x				x		No. Podcasts - videos	10
<p>Date: once a year the series Communication tactical procedures:</p> <p>Series Launch Announcement - Promote the launch on social media and the website with an introduction to the series, themes, and featured speakers or topics.</p> <p>Dedicated Web Page - Create a page on the website with episodes, descriptions, and streaming options or download links.</p> <p>Email and Social Media Teasers - Send emails and share clips or quotes from episodes on social media to build interest before each release.</p> <p>Regular Episode Posts - Announce each new episode on LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram, highlighting key topics or guest insights.</p> <p>Cross-Promotion with Partners - Encourage partner organizations to share episodes on their platforms to expand reach.</p> <p>Engagement and Feedback - Invite listeners to share their thoughts in comments or surveys to gather feedback and improve future content.</p> <p>Recap and Highlights - Post monthly or quarterly highlights of popular episodes on the website and in newsletters.</p>									

Joint actions with others EU project(s)	x	x	x					No. Actions	1
<p>Date: at least once during project / recommended December 2025</p> <p>Communication tactical procedures:</p> <p>Joint Action Announcements - Post announcements on social media and the website detailing the purpose, objectives, and partners involved in each EU joint action.</p> <p>Dedicated Web Section - Create a section on the website to showcase joint actions, including descriptions, goals, and updates on progress.</p> <p>Email Updates to Stakeholders - Send targeted emails to inform relevant stakeholders about upcoming joint actions and encourage participation or collaboration.</p> <p>Social Media Highlights - Share regular updates, visuals, and milestones from joint actions on LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram to keep audiences engaged.</p> <p>Cross-Promotion with EU Partners - Coordinate with EU partners to share updates through their networks, maximizing visibility across member states.</p> <p>Press Releases for Major Milestones - Issue press releases to highlight key achievements or results of joint actions that have broad EU relevance.</p> <p>End-of-Year Recap - Publish a summary of all joint actions and their outcomes on the website and in a year-end newsletter.</p>									
Documentary	x	x	x	x				No. documentary	3
<p>Date: once a year</p> <p>Communication tactical procedures:</p> <p>Pre-Release Teasers - Share behind-the-scenes content, trailers, or short clips on social media a month before release to build excitement.</p> <p>Dedicated Website Page - Create a page on the project website with documentary details, trailers, release dates, and streaming options.</p> <p>Launch Event - Host an online or in-person premiere event with a Q&A session featuring the researchers;</p> <p>Email Announcements - Send a launch email to subscribers with a synopsis, trailer, and viewing link to drive immediate interest.</p> <p>Social Media Campaign - Post highlights, key quotes, and visuals from the documentary across LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram for ongoing promotion.</p> <p>Partner and Network Promotion - Collaborate with partner organizations to share the documentary with their audiences.</p> <p>Post-Release Discussion - Organize online discussions or panels to engage viewers and deepen the impact of the documentary's themes.</p>									
Briefs and technical reports for the target audiences		x	x	x	x	x		No. Articles	6
<p>Date: at least every 9 months</p> <p>Communication tactical procedures:</p> <p>Website Repository - Create a dedicated section on the project website where all briefs and technical reports are available for download, organized by topic or theme.</p>									

Email Distribution to Stakeholders - Send targeted emails to relevant stakeholders, with summaries and direct links to the reports.

Social Media Highlights - Share key insights, statistics, and visuals from each report on LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook, tagging relevant organizations.

Partner Amplification - Encourage partner organizations to distribute the reports through their channels, newsletters, and social media for broader reach.

Press Release for High-Impact Reports - Issue a press release for reports with significant findings or policy implications to reach media outlets.

Follow-Up Webinars or Q&A Sessions - Host online discussions to review the findings with experts, providing deeper engagement with the report’s content.

Feedback Collection - Include a link for reader feedback on the website to improve future reports and ensure they meet audience needs.

News and articles								x	No News and Articles	20
-------------------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	---	----------------------	----

Date: at least every 4 months
 Communication tactical procedures:

Website Media Section - Create a “Media Coverage” page on the website to showcase articles, interviews, and news mentions, with links to the original sources.

Email Alert to Stakeholders - Send an email to subscribers and stakeholders with a brief summary and links to recent media features, highlighting the project’s visibility.

Social Media Shout-Outs - Share news articles and interviews on LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram, tagging the media outlet and relevant project partners to expand reach.

Cross-Promotion with Partners - Encourage partners and collaborators to share media mentions through their networks and social media platforms.

Press Mentions in Newsletter - Include a “Project in the News” section in the quarterly newsletter with summaries and links to all recent media coverage.

Quote Graphics - Design visuals with impactful quotes or key takeaways from the media piece, and post them on Instagram to engage followers.

Media Recap - Publish an end-of-year recap of all significant media mentions and coverage on the website and in an annual newsletter.

Table 15: KPI’s according to Communication Channels (until December 2025)

Communication Channels	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Impact Indicator	Target value
Public Website	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Visits per month	Average of 120
								Downloads per publication	Average of 100
								Visits by origin	From all EU countries
Instagram	x	x	x	x					

								New followers per year	100
								New posts per month	5-10
								Page visits per month	100
								Engagement Rate	3%
LinkedIn	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	New followers per year	100
								New posts per month	5-10
								Page visits per month	50
Facebook	x	x	x	x			x	New friends per year	100
								New posts per month	5-10
								Page visits per month	100
E-newsletter	x	x	x	x			x	Issues per year	3
									100-200
								New subscriptions per year	
								Subscription from widening countries per year	10%
Press releases							x	No. Press release	20
Press media, articles and other platforms	x	x	x	x	x		x	No. Articles	20/year
Podcasts/audio/vídeo	x	x	x	x	x			Listeners/viewer per edition	100-200

4. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

The exploitation strategy is positioned at developing a sustainable exit plan to efficiently exploit tangible and intangible project results towards maximizing impact. **Exploitation will be initiated at the beginning of the project and will extend beyond the project's lifetime.** The Exploitation Strategy will be developed under WP5 and Task 5.1 in order to ensure the development of CONCILIARE strategies to address barriers to maximizing impact and propose the post-project strategies to ensure long-term sustainability of the project results.

The Exploitation strategy of the CONCILIARE project will pave the way towards future exploitation of the results generated by creating an attractive knowledge portfolio to continue enhancing the innovations after the end of the project. Three main exploitation dimensions –**societal, scientific-technical and political**–will guide the activities to be further updated according to the pilot trial results and evidence-based knowledge acquired.

Societal exploitation will contemplate the creation of formative and work experiences in CCIs through the engagement of UM students in the co-creation of media materials. The scientific and technical exploitation includes 1) provision of replicable methodologies tested for their effectiveness in promoting confidence in CCH changes across cultural contexts; 2) provision of user-friendly and engaging multimedia materials to address changes in CCH (also applicable to other types of heritage) by educational and museum stakeholders; political exploitation will comprise the provision of recommendations for EU, national and local policymakers working to encourage uptake of the evidence-based recommendations in heritage related policies.

Approach: This strategy will guarantee the creation of robust exploitation plans at the end of the project. UM will cooperate with all partners for the exploitation strategy. The methodology is based on a step-wise approach: 1) preliminary identification by the consortium of expected exploitable results; 2) assessment of the innovation and potential end users of key exploitable results; 3) prioritization of the main applicable standards in the sector; 4) implementation of the IPR management strategy defined at the beginning of the project in order to identify tentative mechanisms to protect knowledge generated by the partners; 5) generating joint and individual exploitation plans; 6) identification of private and public funding schemes as essential pillars of a fundraising strategy that guarantee the future deployment of the innovations produced in the project. The consortium has planned to apply for the services of the Horizon Results Booster as soon as the first deliverable is ready to receive expert guidance and training to improve the project strategy towards effective identification and exploitation of key exploitable results.

The overall IP approach of the project builds on the principles described in the EC Recommendations on the management of IP in knowledge transfer activities and Code of Practice - along three main aspects: (1) internal IP management, (2) knowledge transfer activities, (3) collaborative and contract research.

Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must –up to four years after the end of the action use their best efforts to **exploit their results** directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, through transfer or licensing.

If, despite a beneficiary's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results.

All the data will be accessible upon request after the embargo period, and all project outputs will be stored in an open repository.

As CONCILIARE project's exploitation strategy is developed, it is planned to resort to the tools offered by the European Commission to help on project's dissemination and exploitation activities:

- Open Research Europe Platform provides a publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, including an open peer review and article revision;
- Horizon Results Booster provides complimentary consulting services, which encompass the development of a dissemination and exploitation strategy for a portfolio, as well as the creation of a business plan and provision of go-to-market support;

-Horizon Results Platform (HRP) is a collection of KER obtained from research and innovation projects funded by the EU. It follows to the exploitation monitoring guidelines specified by the European Commission for Horizon Europe.

Where the call conditions impose **additional exploitation obligations** (including obligations linked to the restriction of participation or control due to strategic assets, interests, autonomy or security reasons), the beneficiaries must comply with them — up to four years after the end of the action (see GA).

Where the call conditions impose additional exploitation obligations in case of a public emergency, the beneficiaries must (if requested by the granting authority) grant, for a limited period of time specified in the request, non-exclusive licenses –under fair and reasonable conditions- to their results to legal entities that need the results to address the public emergency and commit to rapidly and broadly exploit the resulting products and services at fair and reasonable conditions. This provision applies up to four years after the end of the action (see GA).

Exploitation Strategy for CONCILIARE Project

The exploitation strategy for the CONCILIARE project is designed to ensure that the research findings, methodologies, and educational materials generated throughout the project reach a broad and impactful audience. This strategy aims to support sustainable engagement with stakeholders across cultural, educational, and political spheres, facilitating the adoption and integration of the project's insights into ongoing heritage and education practices. By creating user-friendly multimedia resources and clear policy recommendations, the strategy seeks to empower educators, museum stakeholders, and policymakers to address and adapt to evolving understandings of Cultural and Colonial Heritage (CCH). Each phase of the strategy builds on previous efforts, guiding the project from awareness-raising to sustained engagement, and ultimately to policy influence and knowledge-sharing.

Context

The CONCILIARE project operates in a context of growing interest in cultural and colonial heritage across Europe and beyond, where re-examining historical narratives is essential to fostering inclusivity, understanding, and awareness. As the demand for accessible educational resources and informed heritage management practices rises, this project aims to address these needs by providing engaging multimedia materials and practical policy recommendations. The project's consortium, composed of partners from Belgium, Croatia, Finland, Italy, the Netherlands, and Portugal, brings diverse perspectives and expertise to the shared goal of exploring the impacts and evolutions of CCH in contemporary society. This strategy aligns with European and international initiatives that promote cultural preservation and aims to bridge historical understanding with modern educational and political needs, ensuring that CCH and related heritage narratives are thoughtfully integrated into future cultural policies and educational practices.

Objectives

- **Raise Awareness:** Increase public understanding of colonial heritage.
- **Foster Engagement:** Promote active participation from communities across various countries.
- **Influence Policy:** Provide evidence-based recommendations for policymakers.
- **Create Resources:** Develop educational materials to enhance critical thinking about colonial histories.

Target Audiences (TG 1-2-3-4-5-6-7)

- **TG1:** Academic and research community
- **TG2:** Community Cohesion Stakeholders
- **TG3:** Education Stakeholders
- **TG4:** Museums and National Libraries Stakeholders
- **TG5:** Policy and Decision makers
- **TG6:** Citizens and Wider Society
- **TG7:** Media/Press and Journalists

Positioning

Positioning is key for a strategy like the CONCILIARE exploitation plan because it defines how the project's outcomes will be perceived, valued, and ultimately adopted by its target audiences. Effective positioning establishes a clear and compelling identity for the project's resources, ensuring that they stand out amid competing information and resonate with the needs and interests of stakeholders, including educators, cultural institutions, and policymakers. Here are a few reasons why positioning is essential in this context:

1. **Relevance to Diverse Stakeholders:** given that CONCILIARE addresses complex and sensitive topics like Cultural and Colonial Heritage (CCH), positioning ensures that each stakeholder group sees the material as directly relevant to their work. For instance, educators need resources that are accessible and adaptable for different age groups, while policymakers require actionable insights that align with cultural policy frameworks.
2. **Clarity and Focus:** a well-positioned strategy simplifies the project's value proposition, presenting its resources as not only informative but also as practical tools for addressing contemporary issues in heritage management. This clarity makes it easier for stakeholders to understand and trust the project's contributions, fostering stronger adoption and long-term engagement.
3. **Building Credibility and Trust:** positioning the project as a credible, insightful resource on CCH issues builds trust among stakeholders. By consistently aligning with professional standards and addressing real-world challenges, the strategy reinforces the project's reliability and encourages institutions and communities to engage with its materials.
4. **Facilitating Integration into Policy and Practice:** for CONCILIARE's resources to influence policy and educational curricula, they must be positioned as essential tools that meet current needs in heritage discourse and education. Effective positioning helps the project's

recommendations be seen as integral to stakeholder goals, encouraging practical application in museums, schools, and cultural policies.

5. **Ensuring Long-Term Impact:** the right positioning ensures that CONCILIARE's outputs continue to be relevant even after the project ends. By emphasizing the adaptability and importance of its resources, the project can foster sustainable engagement, encouraging stakeholders to use and refer to its materials over time.

Considering this we point Conciliare positioning as:

The CONCILIARE project is positioned as a leading research project for accessible, impactful insights and tools on Cultural and Colonial Heritage, empowering citizens, educators, cultural institutions, and policymakers to foster informed and inclusive heritage practices, while ensuring cross-cultural dialogues and adaptability to evolving cultural needs.

Communication Axis

The communication axis is crucial to implementing CONCILIARE's positioning as it ensures consistent, targeted messaging across channels, building trust and credibility with diverse stakeholders. It allows for tailored engagement with educators, museums, and policymakers, maximizing reach and reinforcing the project's relevance and authority in Cultural and Colonial Heritage topics.

The strategy will prioritize:

- **Transparency:** Sharing project goals and findings openly.
- **Inclusivity:** Ensuring all voices are represented in discussions.
- **Education:** Providing valuable resources to enhance understanding.

Functional Benefits:

- **Educational Resources:** Accessible, high-quality CCH materials for educators and institutions.
- **Policy Guidance:** actionable recommendations for inclusive cultural policies.
- **Engagement Tools:** multimedia resources, workshops, and events to foster dialogue.
- **Knowledge Preservation:** digital archives to document and preserve CCH narratives.

Emotional Benefits:

- **Empowerment:** fosters pride and ownership of cultural heritage.
- **Trust and Inclusion:** builds trust with inclusive, diverse narratives.
- **Connection:** strengthens community ties through shared histories.
- **Inspiration:** encourages reflection and social cohesion.

These benefits make CONCILIARE both informative and emotionally resonant, supporting education and fostering deeper community connections.

Concept and Key Messages + Hashtags

Defining the concept and messages now is fundamental because it establishes a clear, unified direction for the CONCILIARE project's communication and engagement efforts as they begin to scale. With a well-defined concept, the project can convey its purpose consistently across channels, ensuring all stakeholders (educators, policymakers, and cultural institutions...) understand and relate to its goals. Clear messages also help position the project effectively, making its value more evident and compelling to diverse audiences.

We now present a possible concept:

"Echoes of the Past: Shaping Inclusive Futures"

This concept highlights how historical narratives continue to resonate today, inspiring both learning and critical conversation. It emphasizes the importance of engaging with Cultural and Colonial Heritage (CCH) to foster a deeper understanding and connection, while also looking forward to an inclusive future.

Rationale:

"Echoes of the Past" acknowledges that the legacy of history continues to shape our present and demands a critical reflection on how Cultural and Colonial Heritage (CCH) impacts contemporary society. This concept invites audiences to confront the unspoken and often uncomfortable aspects of history, recognizing that to build an inclusive future, we must fully engage with diverse perspectives and untold narratives.

- Echoes of the Past emphasizes that history's impact is ongoing, challenging us to confront inherited biases and understand the structural influences of colonial legacies today.
 - Embracing Heritage goes beyond passive appreciation, encouraging active, sometimes uncomfortable engagement with CCH that questions traditional narratives and acknowledges marginalized voices.
 - Inspiring Dialogue reflects the need for open, critical conversations that bridge generations and cultural divides, fostering understanding while addressing historical inequalities.
 - Shaping Inclusive Futures underscores the project's commitment to reshaping heritage practices and policies, challenging institutions to create narratives that include all voices and foster social accountability.

This concept positions "Echoes of the Past" as more than an educational tool—it's a call to action to reflect, engage, and advocate for a history that acknowledges all perspectives, fostering a more equitable cultural landscape.

Key Messages:

- **Confronting History’s Legacy Today:** The past continues to impact our present, urging us to critically engage with history for a more inclusive future.
- **Transforming Learning into Action:** Our interactive resources not only educate but also challenge individuals to think critically about CCH.
- **Bridging Generations Through Dialogue:** We encourage conversations that respect diverse perspectives, fostering understanding and reconciliation.
- **Redefining Heritage as Inclusive:** By embracing all voices, we reshape the cultural narrative to be representative and just.
- **Inspiring Accountability and Connection:** Understanding heritage cultivates a shared responsibility to promote unity and inclusivity.

Hashtags:

- #EchoesOfThePast
- #Shapinginclusivefuture
- #InclusiveHistory
- #ColonialHeritage
- #InclusiveFuture
- #CommunityVoices
- #HeritageEducation

Communication-Mix

Table 16: Action Plan (Creative Names and Activities)

Phase	Activity (Description and goal)	Objectives and Target	Date	Location
Phase 1: Awareness and Initial Engagement (October 2024 - July 2025)	<p>Coffee Talks Organize casual gatherings in local cafes/or museums and libraries where community members discuss CCH issues.</p> <p>Goal: Create informal dialogue spaces and build local awareness about colonial heritage.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness</p> <p>Foster Engagement</p> <p>–</p> <p>TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG6</p>	From December 2024. Each month in different countries for Conciliare Partners	Cafes/Museums/Libraries from different countries of Conciliare Partners.
	<p>Voices from the Past: Public Lectures Invite experts to deliver lectures on colonial history in universities, libraries and cultural events engaging students and the academic</p>	<p>Raise Awareness</p> <p>Foster Engagement</p> <p>–</p>	Every 3 months, from February 2025	In a city recommended from each partner.

	community. Goal: Educate and engage academic audiences on colonial topics.	TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG6, TG7		
	Echoes in Audio: Podcast Series Create a podcast featuring personal narratives related to colonial heritage, amplifying diverse voices. Goal: Reach a broader audience with personal stories.	Raise Awareness Create Resources – TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG7	March 2025. Ten episode series, every 6 months	Instagram, Facebook.
	Historical Heritage Exhibits in Schools Install small exhibits in schools showcasing artefacts and narratives on colonial history for educational purposes. Goal: Connect young audiences with historical context.	Raise Awareness Foster engagement – TG2, TG3, TG6, TG7	The exhibition can be itinerant, visiting different schools in the same region. May 2025	In a city where research is being conducted (e.g. Faro).
	Voices Amplified: Awareness Campaigns Launch campaigns on social and local media to raise awareness about colonial heritage and its significance. Goal: Inform the general public and create widespread engagement.	Raise Awareness Foster engagement – TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG7	Every year. Starting June 2025	Digital Campaign / Online oriented for each country of the project.
	Introductory Webinars on Colonial Heritage Host webinars introducing the basics of colonial heritage studies for educators, students, and the public. Goal: Provide accessible education for newcomers to heritage topics.	Foster Engagement Create Resources – TG1, TG2, TG3, TG5	Every 6 months. June 2025	Online.
Phase 2: Deeper Engagement and Knowledge Building (August 2025 to March 2026)	Heritage Unplugged: Community Workshops Hold workshops for community discussions on local perspectives of colonial history, promoting intercultural dialogue, as new research results are being known. Goal: Build understanding through discussions	Foster Engagement – TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG6, TG7	Every 3 months, from September 2025	Local cultural entity chosen by a partner of Conciliare.

	<p>Teaching Through Time Develop and distribute educational materials on colonial heritage tailored for schools. Goal: Provide resources for education, empowering teachers and students with historical context.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement Create Resources – TG2, TG3, TG5 TG6, TG7</p>	<p>October 2025</p>	<p>To be distributed in countries selected by partners.</p>
	<p>Reel Reflections: Echoes for the Future Film Screenings Screen documentaries on colonial heritage followed by moderated discussions. Goal: Raise awareness through visual storytelling.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement Create Resources – All TGs</p>	<p>November 2025</p>	<p>Launch in a specific city of the consortium (e.g Braga, in The Teatro Circo).</p>
	<p>Event “Shaping Futures 2026” plan presentation / findings Communication Goal: Uncover findings of Conciliare, share information about 2026 plan, while promoting discussion and dialogue</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement – All TGs</p>	<p>December 2025</p>	<p>University of Minho, Braga, 2026.</p>
	<p>Shaping Futures Merchandising from invited artists from different countries that will develop a message for simple items (t-shirt, bags, bottles..) related to findings of the projects Goal: Create impact in the community spreading messages through merchanding that will have social impact</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement Create Resources – All TGs</p>	<p>January 2026</p>	<p>Across different countries and communicated in all medias.</p>
	<p>Heritage Live: Instagram Lives Host live Instagram discussions with experts and community members on heritage topics, with real-time Q&A. Goal: Engage the online audience interactively.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement – All TGs</p>	<p>February 2026 7 lives in a week.</p>	<p>At least host from each partner, on Instagram.</p>

	<p>Cultural Heritage Tours Organize guided tours of heritage sites with discussions on their colonial significance. Goal: Provide experiential learning through hands-on interaction</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement Create Resources – TG2, TG3, TG6, TG7</p>	<p>March 2026</p>	<p>Cities selected from partners, where research is being done.</p>
	<p>Digital Archive Project Create a digital archive where community members contribute photos, stories, and documents related to heritage. Goal: Preserve and share historical records.</p>	<p>Create Resources – All TGs</p>	<p>April 2026</p>	<p>Online (promoted on social media and by press releases).</p>
<p>Phase 3: Consolidation and Collaboration (April 2026 and after December 2026)</p>	<p>Urban Echoes: Interactive Exhibits Collaborate with museums to create interactive exhibits that explore colonial narratives, making heritage accessible to all. The opening event will hold a presentation, where new findings are presented and where regulators and media will be invited. Goal: Engage community visually with heritage themes.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement Create Resources – All TGs</p>	<p>May 2026</p>	<p>Museums selected from partners, where research is being done.</p>
	<p>Educational Video Series Release a video series explaining project findings, tailored for educators and policymakers. Goal: Support educators and policymakers in understanding project insights</p>	<p>Raise awareness Create Resources – All TGs</p>	<p>July 2026</p>	<p>Across all countries of partners.</p>
	<p>Shaping Connections: Annual Conference Final conference where stakeholders discuss project progress, findings, and future heritage initiatives.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement Create Resources</p>	<p>September 2026</p>	<p>Hold by an University of the Consortium.</p>

	<p>Goal: Facilitate collaboration and knowledge-sharing.</p>	<p>– All TGs</p>		
	<p>Best Practices Guide Publish a guide with recommendations for policymakers and cultural organizations on addressing colonial heritage. Goal: Provide actionable insights for institutions.</p>	<p>Create Resouces – TG2, TG3, TG5, TG6, TG7</p>	<p>November 2026</p>	<p>Across different countries and communicated in all medias.</p>
	<p>Special Issue Publish focused research articles in high-ranking journals, increasing scholarly awareness. Publishing event will be hold by a partner responsible for edition. Goal: Contribute to academic literature on colonial heritage.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Create Resources – TG1, TG7</p>	<p>December 2026</p>	<p>To be defined by partner.</p>
	<p>Echoes Shape the Future Book Book to hold the research developed during the project, with public presentation Goal: Foster reflection and dialogue on historical impacts.</p>	<p>Raise awareness Create Resouces – All TGs</p>	<p>January 2027</p>	<p>The event will take place at the same time, in different cities.</p>
	<p>Final / Closure Conciliare with Documentary Presentation Goal: Foster reflection and dialogue on historical impacts.</p>	<p>Raise Awareness Foster Engagement Create Resouces – All TGs</p>	<p>February 2027</p>	<p>Presence in the venue of all participants of the project. To be defined.</p>

ANNEX 1: C&D GUIDELINE FOR PARTNERS

To ensure consistency and professionalism across all communication products associated with the project, the following guidelines have been provided to partners. These guidelines cover the preparation of various communication deliverables, including the project reporting document, logo usage, and contributions to the project website.

1. Project Deliverable Document tyle

Partners are required to submit word documents detailing the progress and deliverables of the project. A Project Management Handbook has been provided to streamline this process, which defines specific editorial styles and document settings. The handbook outlines the main compositional characteristics, including font types, sizes, margins, headings, and spacing. Partners are expected to strictly adhere to these predefined styles to ensure uniformity across all reports. The document includes a table with clear formatting information and instructions about how to use fonts throughout the documents (Table 17). This approach ensures that all reports are comprehensive, easy to follow, and consistent in presentation.

Table 17: Project Deliverable Document tyle

Document	Project management handbook
Document title formatting	Font Arial 28 pt bold Colour: brown
Title formatting	Font Arial 18 pt bold Colour: brown
Subtitle formatting	Font Arial 12 pt bold Colour: brown
Third level title formatting	Font Arial 12 pt italic Colour: brown
Paragraph formatting	Font Arial 11 pt regular Colour: black
Emphasis text formatting	Font Arial 11 pt italic Colour: black
Emphasis text 2 formatting	Font Arial 11 pt bold Colour: black
Quotes formatting	Font Arial 10 pt italic Colour: black
Caption formatting	Font Arial 10 pt regular Colour: black
References formatting	Font Arial 10 pt bold Colour: grey

2. Logo Usage Guidelines

Clear instructions have been provided regarding the correct use of the project logo in various contexts. The logo is available in different color schemes (full color, black, and white) and orientations (horizontal and vertical) (Figure 21). Partners must ensure that the logo is used appropriately based on the context, and they should respect the specified clear space around the logo when it is placed near other graphic elements (Figure 22). This clear space is critical to maintain the logo's visibility and impact, preventing it from being overshadowed or distorted by surrounding content. The guidelines also prohibit any alterations to the logo's proportions or colors, ensuring that the brand identity remains intact across all platforms and materials.

Figure 21: Logo in color and black and white

conciliare
confidently changing colonial heritage

conciliare
confidently changing colonial heritage

conciliare
confidently changing colonial heritage

Figure 22: Logo in context

3. Contributions to the Website

Partners have been actively involved in creating content for the website, contributing text and sourcing images. This process is still ongoing, with images being collected, evaluated, and shared among the partners. All contributions should align with the project's overarching messaging and visual identity, ensuring that the website presents a cohesive and polished appearance. Partners are encouraged to collaborate closely to provide high-quality, relevant content that reflects the project's objectives and progress.

By following these guidelines, all partners can contribute to a unified and professional presentation of the project, ensuring that all communication products effectively represent the project's goals and values.

This document is the first version of the CONCILIARE Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (CDE). It will be continuously updated during the course of the project. The CDE is designed to meet the consortium academic and technical needs.